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Presidential Remarks

I-Chun Fan

Academia Sinica, TAIWAN

In the seven years since the Asian Network for GIS-based Historical Studies (ANGIS) was founded in December 2012, we have made great progress in scientific discoveries in historical studies. Through the efforts of our members, participants, and volunteers, academic activities such as annual meetings and international conferences have been successfully held in the past six years. In addition, innovative research results have been published in the peer-reviewed E-Journal of the Asian Network for GIS-based Historical Studies (JANGIS) with the support of an efficiently organized editorial committee. In this 2019 volume, there are papers concerning changes in land use, urbanization, and land surface temperature using remote sensing and spatial analysis. The integration of domain knowledge including humanities and social science with GIS technology will expand our vision and encourage new findings. All these have made ANGIS thrive and become more focused. With the importance of GIS-based research for historical studies we intend to invite those who do research on fundamental and practical issues of historical studies, and to encourage more participants including stakeholders, entrepreneurs, professionals, scholars, and students from different backgrounds who are interested in the domain of historical studies with GIS methods to join in the conference, journal and other relevant activities of ANGIS for the purpose of expanding interdisciplinary and multi-disciplinary collaboration in Asia. We are looking forward to having your comments and suggestions and having more opportunities to discuss, and exchange ideas and experiences for future development in this area.

Fan, I-Chun

[Prof. I-Chun FAN]
December, 2019

A Note from General Secretary - ANGIS

Dear Friends and Colleagues,

After almost a decade since the starting of the ANGIS (The Asian Network of GIS-based Historical Studies), it is facing a turning point. As every society in the world, ANGIS has come to a stage when the leadership to run it should be passed to a new generation. I, the general secretary of the ANGIS, retired from the University of Tokyo in 2018. Prof. I-Chun Fan is going to retire from the Academia Sinica in a few years, and some of the other old members are approaching the retiring age. The situation surrounding GIS-related studies seems to be also entering a new stage. With the conspicuous improvement of the GIS environment, GIS becomes far more accessible to many academics. Though there are still lots of opportunities for GIS-based studies to make a break-through in many conventional fields, I feel the initial stage that the ANGIS has played is over and we should decide which direction we should move forward. At this point, I am happy to find some young scholars like Biplab Biswas and Tomoko Shiroyama are emerging as leaders of large scale projects centering on GIS- topics. I should add more research activities are coming up not only in Japan but also in other countries.

The present JANGIS is the product by the editorship of Biplab Biswas, for which I am truly grateful. Some articles contained here show the exemplary cases of GIS-based studies. For many of us working with spatial analysis, publishing in paper-type books has still many hurdles. JANGIS will still a have role to play in coming years under the situation. Support and collaboration from the members and readers are essential to maintain JANGIS.

Tsukasa Mizushima
Professor Emeritus
The University of Tokyo

The Asian Network for GIS-based Historical Studies, Asia or ANGIS (Asia)

1. The Asian Network for GIS-based Historical Studies, Asia, (hereafter “ANGIS (Asia)”) is a network for all academics interested in GIS-based historical studies on Asia. It serves as an umbrella network composed of various research groups or institutions (hereafter “units”) in the same field.
2. ANGIS (Asia) was founded in December 2012, to serve the needs of units or members wishing to promote GIS-based historical studies on Asia by exchanging ideas, techniques, or sources.
3. ANGIS (Asia) organizes an annual international conference.
4. ANGIS (Asia) organizes an editorial committee to publish E-Journal annually.
5. Other activities may be proposed by the units or members at the annual general meeting of ANGIS (Asia) to be held during the annual international conference.

ANGIS office is born by the office-bearers of ANGIS (JAPAN), the national unit of the ANGIS in Japan for two years till the end of November 2014. From that point onward, the national unit of the ANGIS is moved to Taiwan, and new office-bearers of ANGIS (Taiwan) continually run for four years till December 2019.

Economic Geography of Joint Stock Companies in British India, 1907-1938

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Abstract: This article reviews the rapid growth of joint stock companies in colonial India by investigating a large set of historical data during the period 1907-1938. Having indicated the numbers of companies and firms, situation of their main offices, and composition of industries, the authors delineates several trends such as a tendency towards spatial dimension, sectoral differentiation, regional specialization, and a growing correlation between the regional economy and the world economy. One of the findings indicates that Calcutta and Bombay were the most prominent cities in the agglomeration of joint stock companies, which had intimately connected to the domestic markets and the world markets. Furthermore, they suggest that East India and Western India experienced a “monocentric” pattern of agglomeration while North India and South India did a “polycentric” pattern of agglomeration in terms of the geography of economic industries. These features are also derived from the geography of indigenous market towns in colonial India suggested by some historians.

Keywords: Joint Stock Company, British India, Economic Geography, Agglomeration.

1. Introduction

The historical sources mention the location of the main offices of private firms and companies in the parts of Asia in the 1900s and 1930s (Thacker’s Indian Directory 1908, 1936; Directory and Chronicle for China, etc., 1908, 1936). According to the *Directories*, the commercial companies operated mainly in either British colonies, or cities which had fallen under the de facto control of the Western powers. In particular, British India was one of the greatest economic regions in Asia before the Second World War, in which Calcutta took the first place in the massive concentration of private firms and companies ^[1]. Bombay also performed as an economically dynamic hotspot despite it fell back in the rankings behind Hong Kong, Shanghai, and Manila in 1936. Perhaps these facts have never universally been approved and imprinted on the study of economic history though studies of “intra-Asian trade” have already made a greater progress. The aim of this article is to describe and explain the marked increase of the scale and scope of corporate enterprise in India between the two World Wars.

Scholars have devoted much energy to numerous debates on the performance of the modern secondary sector and the nature of government policies associated with it during these periods. Before and after the First World War, India’s considerable industrial development occurred through a policy of import-substituting industrialization. Its pace was faster after 1914, partly due to the erection of high tariff barriers afforded to specific domestic industries. More recently, many studies have focused on different subjects in economic geography relating to industrial impact upon the urbanization,

location and spatial distribution of industries, the making of industrial complex, patterns of modern industrialization, and the analysis of several specific industries in India (Sharma and Tiwari 2014). These works and methodologies were coming to relate to studies on the subcontinent’s economic history.

One example is Ray’s work on private investment in colonial India. Ray argues that many established industries were concentrated in Calcutta, Bombay and their hinterlands, and that the two provinces continued to enjoy as much as 78 per cent of total investment in India till 1941-42 (Ray 1979, 47-49). More interestingly, Ray stresses that new ventures during and after 1914 were undertaken by Indian industrialists freshly risen from the older indigenous sector that had long occupied a large share in India’s domestic economy, and also suggests the historical origins of the Indian capitalist class and many of its characteristics to this day (Ray 1984, 1988). They came almost exclusively from certain merchant communities that had migrated over the subcontinent. Ray focuses upon a largely autonomous “bazaar” money and commodity market in which Indian industrialists continued to be heavily involved even in the late colonial period.

Operating through order indigenous devices, Ray argued that the bazaar bankers and merchants enabled agricultural production, credit transfers, and commodity exchanges between certain inland market places often far removed from each place ^[2]. This integrated indigenous system functioned through the networks of the commercial centres, the market towns, and the rural periodical markets, which was intimately connected by roads, railways, inland water transports, and telegraph.

The great money centres were the noble points of an all-India economic system, which were headed by Calcutta and Bombay serving as capitals not merely of colonial economy but also of the bazaar economy. The twin centres had interwoven trading and financial transactions with other important centres such as Madras, Karachi, Delhi, Cawnpore, Amritsar, Lahore, Ahmedabad, Cochin, Tuticorin, and Chittagong. These commercial centres kept in touch with the market towns linked to the smaller rural towns, which led to the geographical clustering of economic activities scattered over the subcontinent. From Ray's study, we can find that there was a polycentric agglomeration of great cities and their surrounding lower density hinterlands in colonial India.

Furthermore, Roy explores regional distribution of industries in India, by surveying small-scale and large-scale industries on the basis of governmental statistics (Roy 2011, pp. 162-63) ^[3]. He explains that nearly half the employment in small-scale industry was located in the United Provinces, Punjab, and Madras, the industry's spatial concentration reflected its dependence on traditional markets and skills available locally. There were certain regional centres to serve the development of labour-intensive industrialization in India. Roy also made a rough map showing some small-scale industry clusters almost exclusively in colonial India. Meanwhile, Roy points out that large-scale industry was concentrated in Bombay and Bengal and that its spatial concentration reflected its dependence on ports and banks. He found that after 1914 Calcutta and Bombay were rapidly becoming specialized in the service industry, such as communications and finance, and were increasingly integrating their surrounding hinterlands into their sphere of influence. Yet, there has not been a systematic attempt to quantify and to describe the evolution of large-scale industries and services in India. This article seeks to do this, based upon a more quantitative dataset of private corporate enterprise in colonial India. We attempt to use these objectively consistent data to sketch a spatial distribution of the commercial and financial networks across the land.

While Ray and Roy have used the traditional methods for identifying the centres of international and domestic business in colonial India, we draw upon Geographical Information System (GIS) to infer the geographical factors and additional economic variables systematically. Thus, we seek to illustrate the geography patterns and trends in performance of corporate enterprise in colonial India. Firstly, we introduce details of data used in this article. Secondly, we examine the rapid growth of joint stock companies in the subcontinent on the basis of much historical data during the period 1907-1937. Having investigated this number of companies and firms, the situation of their main offices, and the composition of their industries, we delineate several trends such as a tendency towards spatial dimension, sectoral differentiation, regional specialization, and a growing correlation between India's domestic economy and its international economy.

2. Details of Data

The validity of any statistical analysis will rely upon the quality of the data available. Since there are comprehensive data on private corporate enterprise in colonial India, we can develop a straight strategy and method to identify salient features of the region's industrial economic geography. We begin with analyzing the basic sources from the *Joint Stock Companies in British India and the Indian States* (henceforth *Joint Stock Companies*) published by Department of Commercial Intelligence and Statistics, the Government of India. It covers quantitative data of corporate enterprise relating to undivided British India between 1906 and 1943, inclusive of the Princely States (Mysore, Baroda, Gwalior, Hyderabad, Indore, and Travancore). After the year 1938-39, Burma was excluded from these statistics due to its separation from British India. This voluminous source provides much information as follows: number of companies at work, their names, the dates of their incorporation, their capital (authorized, subscribed, and paid-up), their objects, and the location of their registered offices.

The dataset *Joint Stock Companies* contains information on approximately 225,000 companies registered in the subcontinent in the early decades of the twentieth century. Each company is listed with information including name of company, classification of business, date of registration, amount of capital, and address of head office. In addition, if a company is a private company, its name is written in italics. The classification of business has three tiers and 46 industries in the third tier. The broad category includes 11 sectors: Banking, Loan and Insurance; Transit and Transport; Trading and Manufacturing; Mills and Presses; Tea and other Planting Companies; Mining and Quarrying; Estate, Land and Building; Breweries and Distilleries; Sugar (including Jaggery) manufacture; Hotels, Theatre and Entertainments; and other Companies). These sectors are further broken down into one or more subdivisions. For example, the sector "Banking, Loan and Insurance" includes the following four subdivisions: Banking; Loan; Investment and Trust; Nidhi and Chit Associations; and Insurance. The category "Nidhi and Chit Associations" is one that belonged to the very small-scale indigenous cooperative credit sector peculiar to the Madras Presidency. The information on capital includes authorized, subscribed and paid-up capital ^[4].

Concerning the companies' address, some examples give us more information on "building/house number", "street/ward", "city", "district", and "presidency/provinces/states" as follows: "AA House, 10, CANNING STREET, CALCUTTA, BENGAL." This pattern of description is commonly seen in the place where many companies were located, such as in the centre of Calcutta or along the famous streets of Bombay. In some cases, on the other hand, the name of the district or the city is only written. This pattern of description is often observed in the address of companies located in relatively small cities.

Even in some cases of Calcutta-based companies, we can nevertheless find the city’s name “Calcutta” written more simply. This dataset does not offer the companies’ address in standardized expression form.

In this study, we focused on the address information and analyzed the geographical distribution of joint stock companies in 1925 and 1937 [5]. The data mentions where the main office of each company was located in parts of the subcontinent, which defines the agglomeration of corporate enterprise by region. As mentioned above, however, the description of the address is not unified. If they are converted into analyzable location information as they are, areas in which there is a large difference in spatial size are treated equally, and as a result, it becomes a constraint to spatial analysis. For the purpose, it is necessary to unify the resolution of address information. Since it was possible to identify the district of almost all companies from the addresses, we unified the resolution of address information at the district level. The boundary of each district is in accordance with the *Imperial Gazetteer of India*, Atlas 1931 edition (Meyer 1931). In the case of a state for which “district” was not established, a similar administrative unit whose boundary can be confirmed was used.

We can thus identify to what extent levels of urbanization expanded vertically rather than horizontally. By using GIS techniques, we illustrate India’s industrial economic geography more exactly on maps. By using the *Joint Stock Companies* dataset, we provide systematic and comprehensive results that are consistent if somewhat challenging. Our method has a novelty in this regard. On the other hand, others will argue that our method accounts for nothing about the exact places of business since the *Joint Stock Companies* provides their registered offices solely. They may also comment that the location available do not correspond to the place of factories and plantations at work. This is an important criticism. But our strength lies in the application of the quantitative sources for identifying network connectivity and related factors between the leading trade centres and their surrounding suburban hinterlands in colonial India. We do encourage Ray’s and Roy’s arguments to add to our dataset of joint stock companies by using analytical method. Our approach leads to indicate the well-established patterns of historical economic geography in India.

3. Corporate Enterprise in Colonial India

3.1 Rupee-Based and Non-Rupee-Based Companies

As suggested before, we use the *Joint Stock Companies* as a basis for estimating the growth of scale and scope of corporate enterprise in colonial India. Here, we begin with delineating tendencies toward the rupee-based / non rupee-based joint stock companies by the nine provinces and the eleven business sectors. The data between 1894 and 1905 are available in the *Financial and*
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Commercial Statistics of British India, which can be connected to a large set of our data from 1906. Fig. 1 and 2 summarize the growth of corporate enterprise in India prior to independence.

Over these four decades, three growth phases can be identified. The first phase, lasting until 1913, was one of a sustained increase in number, which was almost exclusively dominated by the three principal presidencies. Interestingly, the Madras presidency took the lead between 1904 and 1908. Their growth actually took off only in the latter part of the 1900s each year. The Swadeshi movement (1905-8), which was much more stringent in Bengal than elsewhere, gave an added impetus to this process. The result was the birth of a number of corporate enterprises founded newly by Indian merchants and entrepreneurs through India, especially in Bengal (Tripathi and Jumani eds., 2007, pp. 79-84). Another push factor was the enactment of the Indian Companies Act, 1913 (Act No. 7 of 1913), which provided many salutary reforms relative to incorporation, regulation, and winding up of trading companies and association in British India (Tripathi and Jumani eds., 2007, p. 87) [6]. This law paved the way for the formation of a number of new joint stock companies.

However, the increase was not a smoothly running continuous one, and the number of companies stagnated during the First World War (1914-1918). In 1914, the number of the companies discontinued in India was 310 while the number of new companies was 112. The First World War, nevertheless, also saw the steady increase of rupee-based companies registered in Bengal.

Fig. 1. Number of Rupee-based Joint Stock Companies by Province and Sector, 1894-1938

Notes: (1) Excluding Burma from 1937; (2) Banking, Loan and Insurance: banking and loan, and insurance, (3) Trading & Manufacturing: printing, public service (gas, water, electric light power, and telephone), tobacco, iron/steel/shipbuilding, building and constructing materials (clay, stone, cement, lime, and others), trading agencies &c.; (4) Mills & Presses: cotton mills, cotton ginning, pressing, bailing, etc., jute mills, jute presses, etc., mills for wool, silk, hemp, etc., paper mills, rice mills, flour mills, saw & timber mills, oil mills, other mills & presses.

(Sources: *Joint Stock Companies* 1903; 1907-38).

The year 1919 was a turning point. In the second phase between 1919 and 1926, dozens of the rupee-based companies were incorporated in British India and the Indian States. Between 1922 and 1926, their number remained relatively stable. In this phase, Bengal had about half of all companies, followed by Bombay. The final phase stood apart from colonial India's earlier experience in the magnitude of increase in number. From 1926 to 1935, Bengal saw a more substantial increase of the registered companies than Bombay and Madras. At the same time, we find a steady increase in other provinces and states outside the three presidencies. There, new companies were founded, especially in the United Provinces, Punjab, Delhi, and the Travancore State. We thus assume that India did not undergo the Great Depression, beginning in the United States in 1929 and becoming a world-wide economic depression during the 1930s, in terms of corporate enterprise over these periods [7].

Fig. 1 also gives the number of the rupee-based companies by sector. We deprive the importance of the India's two principal sectors from the data: "Trading and

Manufacturing" and "Banking, Loan, and Insurance". These account for 77.4% of all the sectors in 1913, 73.3% in 1925, and 79.0% in 1937. "Trading and Manufacturing" increased rapidly between the two World Wars, especially from 1926 onwards. The numbers rose up from 840 companies in 1913 to 4,522 companies in 1937. From the early 1930s, in particular, there was the growing sectors of "Printing, Publishing & Stationary", "Engineering", "Chemicals & Allied Trades", "Iron, Steel, and Shipbuilding", "Public Service Companies", and "Agencies (including managing agent companies)". By 1938, the numbers of "Building and Contracting Materials", "Tanneries and Leather Trade", "Tobacco", "Soap, Candle", and "Match" companies also increased steadily.

The second group, "Banking, Loan, and Insurance" expanded rapidly from 1925 to 1932 and reached a peak of the boom in 1936. Its numbers were 766 companies in 1913, 1,062 companies in 1925, and 3,273 companies in 1936. In this sector, "Banking and Loan" was an overwhelming majority, but "Insurance" increased rapidly from 1931 onwards.

The third sector was made up by "Mills and Presses", which increased from 518 companies in 1913 to 960 companies in 1936. This sector comprised "Cotton Mills", "Cotton Ginning, Pressing, and Bailing Mills", "Jute Mills", "Rice Mills", and "Oil Mills". The first two categories were the most important in this sector. In the rest, there were several growing sectors such as "Tea and Other Planting", "Mining and Quarrying", "Transit & Transport", "Estate, Land, and Building", and "Hotels, Theatres, and Entertainments". More interestingly, "Hotels, Theatres, and Entertainments" rose at almost same rate as the number of "Transit & Transport" and "Tea and Other Planting" in the late 1930s. This fact would result from the process of urban economic development in various parts of colonial India. Furthermore, the number of "Sugar (including Jaggery)" also increased drastically from 48 companies in 1931 to 199 in 1936.

In the background, there were British colonial measures to design an industrialization policy in the 1920s and 1930s. As Tomlinson argued, the reconstruction of India's budget after the end of the First World War meant augmenting the receipts from taxation, especially customs duties (Tomlinson 1979, p. 62). Consequently, the general duties on imports increased from 7.5% in 1917 to 11% in 1921 and to 15% in 1922, with rates of up to 25% on imports of sugar and luxury goods such as motor vehicles and confectionery. The difficult political and economic conditions of the late 1920s and early 1930s saw further substantial increases in revenue tariffs. The general rate eventually reached 31.25% in 1931, while luxuries paid up to 50%. These levels of revenue tariff had a protective effect upon the domestic market for Indian manufacturers while simultaneously increasing public revenues. The Indian Fiscal Commission (1922) recommended the

establishment of an Indian Tariff Board. In 1924, India opted for ‘discriminating protection’ for a few industries rather than for imperial preference. As many historians points out, this policy gave a further boost to import-substituting industries in colonial India. Between 1923 and 1939, tariff boards granted protection to eleven industries such as iron and steel, cotton textiles, sugar, paper, matches, salt, heavy chemicals, plywood and tea-chests, sericulture, magnesium chloride, and gold thread, and to rice/wheat producers (Tomlinson 1993, pp. 133-34). The results show an increase of the companies in the “Trade and Manufacture”, “Mills and Presses”, and “Sugar (including Jaggery) categories as shown in Fig. 1.

The *Joint Stock Companies* also provides the data on the geography and main business of the non-Rupee companies in India. They were incorporated elsewhere than but worked in India. The numbers increased slowly from 517 companies in 1914 to 881 companies in 1936. The overwhelming majority was of course British, but there was a limited number of French, German, Chinese, and Japanese corporations. The dominant position of Bengal-based companies in India was the most striking feature of the period. Their number rose up from 177 (34.2%) in 1914 to 562 (63.8%) in 1936. The second ranking was the registered companies in the Bombay Presidency, which numbered 131 (25.3%) in 1914 and 239 (26.4%) in 1931. Its numbers began to decrease from 1932, and fell down to 134 companies (15.2%) in 1936.

The composition of business was almost exclusively occupied by the following three sectors: “Banking, Loan, and Insurance” (mainly “insurance”), “Trading & Manufacturing” (mainly “publishing and printing”, “chemicals and allied trades”, “iron, steel and shipbuilding”, “engineering”, “public services”, and “trading agencies”), and “Tea and Other Planting”. In many cases, they saved to carry out the production and transaction of the export-oriented commodities. In the rest, the number of “Transit & Transport” increased at the almost same rate as the numbers of “Mining and Quarrying”. The number of “Mills and Presses” continued to be much smaller.

3.2 Geographical Distribution

Fig. 2 is a set of GIS-based maps for showing the geography of corporate enterprise in colonial India. We focus upon two bigger circles in 1925 and 1937 respectively. In short, Calcutta and Bombay had the largest agglomerations of the registered companies in India. Calcutta was the Imperial Capital until 1911. In 1925, Calcutta city attracted 2,047 companies (39.7%) of all 12,636 companies while Bombay city did 811 companies (15.6%). These two great cities had more than one half of the total number of the registered companies in colonial India, which also stood in a first position and a second position in the concentration of private firms and companies in Asia. There was a significant increase of the companies registered there by 1937. Calcutta had 3,344 companies (30.7%) of all 23,111 companies, Bombay

attracting 1,129 companies (10.1%). Calcutta continued to have the largest number of firms and companies of all the trade centres in Asia.

Fig. 2. Geographical Distribution of Joint Stock Companies in India by District in 1925 and 1937

Note: Place names represent districts where the total number amounted to more than 10 companies in 1925 and 1937 together.

(Source: *Joint Stock Companies*, 1925, Table No. 8, pp. 42-133; 1937, Table No. 6, pp. 55-237).

Fig. 2 also shows concentration areas of corporate enterprise in colonial India. We identify three spatial patterns of agglomerations in 1925: East India (38.3%), South India (24.6%), and Western India (18.2%). But India saw a great diversification in economic geography

by 1937. India’s four largest economic zones accounted for 39.7% of East India, 24.8% of South India, and 16.5% of Western India, and 13.6% of North India. During the 1930s, an increasing amount of significant growth emerged in North India. The twin large circles represent 533 companies in Lahore and 252 companies in Delhi. Furthermore, we find that the increase occurred at the same time in South India, which included Madras city (478 companies) and Coimbatore (276 companies). We propose that East India and Western India experienced a “monocentric” pattern of corporate agglomeration in economic geography during the period 1925-37, while South India and North India in a “polycentric” pattern of corporate agglomeration.

A commercial book of 1937 introduced India’s 56 principal ports and trade centres (Hand Book 1937, pp. 62-117). In 1934/35, six seventh of India’s seaborne (foreign and coastal) trade concentrated in the seven major port-cities—Bombay, Calcutta, Rangoon, Karachi, Madras, Cochin, and Vizagapatam—with a fine harbor and shipping facilities employed in the carrying trade. In particular, Bombay and Calcutta had 58.9% of all the seaborne trade. Trade centres were also situated in the interior of the subcontinent because the population was chiefly rural: Delhi, Lahore, Ahmedabad, Asansol, Lucknow, Amritsar, Cawnpore, Nagpore, and Benares were either distributing or industrial centres with populations of over 200,000. They were important hotspots in the concentration of merchants, commodities, monies, and information from within India and abroad. Their spatial expansion corresponds almost to the geographical distribution of joint stock companies as shown by Fig. 2.

4. Regional Specialization

4.1 East India

Fig. 3 provides GIS-based maps of East India in 1925 and 1937, respectively, in which the position of Calcutta city accords with earlier findings in economic activity. This region had the largest agglomeration of corporate enterprise in colonial India, which ran from Calcutta to the interior of Bengal, Assam, Bihar / Orissa, and Burma. These industrial and agricultural areas were linked with Calcutta through the main lines of the East Indian and Eastern Bengal Railways, and through the water routes along the Hooghly, Ganges, Padma, Brahmaputra, and Meghna Rivers. These transport systems served to generate numerous intertwining networks of corporate enterprise in and out of East India. Therefore, we find a Calcutta-oriented “monocentric” pattern of corporate agglomeration in East India.

In this region, the largest sector was “Trade and Industry” in the two years, represented by a great many “Engineering”, “Chemicals and Allied Trades”, “Agencies (including Managing Agencies Companies)”, “Iron, Steel and Shipping”, and “Clay, Stone, Cement, and other Building Materials”. The most important sector,

though much smaller in term of numbers of companies, was “Tea & Other Planting Companies”, followed by two sectors “Mining & Quarrying” and “Mills & Presses”. By 1937, however, the increasing significant sector is found in “Banking, Loan, and Insurance” in Bengal. Mymensingh, Bogra, Rangpur, and Jalpaiguri experienced an increase of insurance companies registered in these districts.

Fig. 3. Geographical Pattern of Corporate Agglomeration in East India in 1925 and 1937

Note and Source: See Fig. 2.

As Fig. 3 presents, the port-city attracted various kinds of joint stock companies. It served the great jute, tea, and coal industries led by the managing agency companies. In 1925, four sectors—“Trade and Industry (including agencies)”, “Tea and Other Planting”, “Mine and Quarrying”, and “Mills and Presses” —occupied about 80% of all the registered companies. By 1937, however, the composition of industry had highly been diversified. Calcutta saw the newly significant expansion of “Banking, Loan, and Insurance”, “Transit and Transport”, “Estate, Land, and Building”, “Hotels, Theatre, and Entertainments”, and “Sugar”. These sectors grew rapidly in the higher level of urbanization in

Calcutta and its surrounding suburban hinterlands such as 24 Parganas and Howrah.

Here, we find an increasingly changing geographical distribution of corporate enterprise in the interior of Bengal from 1925 to 1937. In 1937, there were the increasing number of the companies registered in Mymensingh (317), Dacca (192), Bogra (112), Jalpaiguri (122), Rangpur (189), and Tippera (171). Dacca and Mymensingh were the important cities in the heart of the jute growing districts. More interestingly, “Banking, Loan, and Insurance” companies took the lead, followed by “Trade and Industry” companies.

Fig. 4 is a set of GIS-Based maps of Western India in 1925 and 1937. We find the great centrality of Bombay City in this region. As stated above, it became one of the principal trade centres in colonial India, owing its importance to its geographical position and to significant natural harbour. Bombay was connected with Gujarat and Northern India by the Bombay, Baroda and Central India Railway, and with Deccan, Central India, and Madras by the Great Indian Peninsula Railway. Along these railways, this region expanded from Bombay to Surat, Ahmedabad, Poona, Sholapur and Dharwar. There were the principal coastal shipping lines calling at Bombay with Karachi, Kathiawar, and the Malabar Coast. Bombay thus served to form a “monopolistic” pattern of agglomeration of corporate enterprise in Western India.

4.2 Western India

In this region, the most important sectors continued to be “Trade and Industry”, followed by “Mills and Presses”, and “Banking, Loan, and Insurance” during these years. These sectors occupied over 70% of all. As Fig. 4 shows, we find the increase of cotton mill and cotton ginning / pressing companies in 1937 not only in Bombay but also its surrounding places such as Ahmedabad, Sholapur, Dharwar, and others.

Fig. 4. Geographical Pattern of Corporate Agglomeration in Western India in 1925 and 1937

Note and Source: See Fig. 2.

By 1937 we find the increase of corporate enterprise in other places. Ahmedabad, with 194 registered companies in 1937, was second to Bombay. The city’s changes from 1925 to 1937 saw the increase in “Banking, Loan, and Insurance” and “Mills and Presses”. This result refers to Oock’s argument that there was a close relationship between mill owners and a small group of indigenous bankers in Ahmedabad (Oock 2014, pp. 63-69). The city preserved its original attitude oriented toward the local markets. The third position was taken by Karachi. It was the gateway of foreign commerce not only for Sind but also for a great part of North-West India, Baluchistan, and Afghanistan. Therefore, this city possessed a significant share of “Banking” and “Trade and Industry” sectors. The growth of Poone is also found especially in two sectors “Trade and Industry” and “Banking, Loan, and Insurance”.

4.3 South India

South India did not experience what happened in East India and Western India, though having a “polycentric” pattern of corporate agglomeration in certain principal trade centres. As shown by Fig. 5, Madras City, the capital of the Madras Presidency, had a smaller concentration of corporate enterprise than Calcutta and Bombay cities, attracting only 198 companies in 1925 and 478 in 1937. In this port-town, more than 60% of them continued to be occupied by two sectors “Banking, Loan, and Insurance” and “Trade and Industry”. By 1937, the “Hotel, Theater, and Entertainment” sector expanded rapidly.

Fig. 5. Geographical Pattern of Corporate Agglomeration in South India in 1925 and 1937

Note and Source: See Fig. 2.

This region witnessed the simultaneous commercial growth of other places such as Coimbatore, Trichinopoly, Tinnevely, Madura, Salem, and South Canara in the Madras Presidency. For example, Coimbatore attracted 177 companies in 1925 and 276 companies in 1937. In 1925, “Banking, Loan, and Insurance” was the largest sector in sheer numbers of companies, over 80% of which were occupied by “Nidhis and Chit Associations” that belonged to the very small-scale indigenous co-operative credit sector peculiar to South India. But by 1937 these indigenous banks had mostly changed into “Banking and Loan” corporations. The numbers of banking companies were also seen in Salem, South Canara, Trichinopoly, and Tanjore. More importantly, the numbers of “Cotton Mills” and “Cotton ginning, pressing, etc.” companies also increased from eight companies in 1925 to 49 companies in 1937. We find Coimbatore as the greatest cotton industrial city in South India.

Furthermore, we identify the rapid increase of companies registered in the State of Mysore (160 to 223

companies), the Malabar District (85 to 150 companies), and the Kingdom of Travancore (184 to 499 companies) in each of the two years. By the transportation system such as rails, roads, and coastal shipping services, these regions were also linked to other trade centres within and outside South India.

4.4 North India

Fig. 6. Geographical Pattern of Corporate Agglomeration in North India in 1925 and 1937

Note and Source: See Fig. 2.

Fig. 6 gives details of corporate agglomeration in North India. This region stretched from central Panjab in the west to the United Provinces in the east. In 1925, many companies, though scattered over the region, were registered in Lahore, Delhi, Cawnpore, and Lucknow. We find that Lahore and Delhi were the most prominent concentration of corporate enterprise in 1937, having attracted 533 companies and 252 companies respectively. More interestingly, the growth of Lahore and Delhi during these periods simultaneously led to the rapid increase of joint stock companies in their surrounding towns such as Amritsar, Ferozepur, Lyallpur, Agra, Meerut, and Aligarh.

By then, North India’s economic geography had a more polycentric aspect because of extensive incorporation in “Trade and Industry”, “Banking, Loan,

and Insurance, and “Hotels, Theaters, and Entertainments. In terms of “Trade and Industry”, it seems that North India was the most dynamic region in India, seeing the quadruple increase of the registered companies for the short interval. In particular, a number of “Printing, Publishing & Stationary”, “Iron, Steel & Shipbuilding”, “Chemicals & Allied Trades”, and “Public Service” companies started business at a remarkable speed.

5. Conclusion

British India had the most massive concentration of private firms and companies in Asia prior to the Second World War. Calcutta took the lead in the number of firms. These features have little been documented by previous studies in Asian economic history. Therefore, we have examined India’s experience of the quite rapid increase of joint stock companies in India between the two Great Wars. One reason for this development was the introduction of the company laws into the subcontinent.

Under a colonial protectionist industrialization policy, the rupee-based companies dominated a significant portion of domestic sectors such as “Trade and Manufacture”, “Mills and Presses”, and “Sugar (including Jaggery). These industries were financed by “Banking and Loan” companies. The Bengal Presidency led to geographic clustering of corporate enterprise during and after the First World War, followed by the Bombay and Madras Presidencies. The companies in other Indian provinces and states also increased gradually from the early 1930s onwards. Meanwhile, a small number of foreign companies were certainly restricted to export-oriented agricultural and industrial sectors, which had the pushing together of corporate activity mostly in the Bengal and Bombay Presidencies.

As noted above, Ray and Roy sketched India’s spatial distributions of the knitting marketing and financial networks between market towns and trade centres across the land. They argued that the commercial networks had increasingly become integrated both horizontally and vertically. By using other quantitative data and a GIS analytical method, we have expanded their conclusions by pointing out both “polycentric” and “monocentric” patterns of agglomeration of corporate enterprise in India during the period 1925-37. Our study provides a comparative perspective relative to geographical clustering in colonial India.

The registered companies in South India and North India, though the relatively small numbers, were spread not only among the coastal port-cities such as Madras, but also expanded into the interior trade centres such as Coimbatore, Bangalore, Lahore, Delhi, Cawnpore, and Lucknow. We have found that South India and North India provides good examples of a “polycentric” agglomeration of multiple trade centres in terms of corporate geography. In East India and Western India, on the other hand, the registered companies were found

disproportionally in Calcutta and Bombay distinguished by the economic and geographical factors that had influenced their location. We have demonstrated that East India and Western India experienced a “monocentric” pattern of corporate agglomeration, in which the greatest industrial clusters were Calcutta and Bombay. Since the early nineteenth century, overseas trade and finance had allowed them to become the two largest commercial / financial port-cities in India. In short, regional economy became more monocentric and unipolar as it became involved strongly and completely into international economy.

Our research is yet too incomplete to resolve around economic geography in colonial India. It does not capture good examples of a growing independent network of colonial or indigenous companies between the trade centres within and outside India. Corporate agglomeration within a specific city is also beyond the scope of this article. Deeper understanding of colonial India’s economic geography will require further study^[8].

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Notes

- [1] In 1908, there were 1,539 companies in Calcutta, 623 in Bombay, 612 in Shanghai, 508 in Hong Kong, 318 in Singapore, 259 in Manila, 251 in Yokohama, 229 in Madras, 197 in Kobe, and 190 in Tientsin. After the Great Depression, however, the proliferation of private companies in parts of Asia accelerated: In 1936, there were 2,422 companies in Calcutta, 2,214 in Shanghai, 1,267 in Hong Kong, 842 in Manila, 827 in Bombay, 606 in Singapore, 491 in Tientsin, 358 in Kobe, 308 in Madras, and 225 in Tokyo.
- [2] Ray used an official publication *Report on Fairs, Markets and Produce Exchanges in India* (published in 1943), which is the most instrumental to understand the geography of about 30,000 agricultural marketplaces such as fairs and markets (hats and mandis) in the subcontinent before independence. They lied mostly within easy reach of main roads, railway stations, or ports of inland waterways and sea, which also served to integrate inland commercial and financial transactions between distant market towns. We think that the periodical markets existed in or around the places where a significant number of joint stock companies also located their head or branch offices.

- [3] Roy describes the long-term pattern of industrialization in India as “labour intensive industrialization” that does not replace artisans with machines but allows the artisans to work harder, improve quality, raise productivity, and contribute to industrial growth.
- [4] If the capital was paid (or authorized/subscribed) in foreign currency, it was written.
- [5] This study has excluded Burma from the analysis. Burma was separated from British India in 1937. The list in 1937 also includes some companies in Burma, but there might be a problem of data coverage.
- [6] The Act of 1913 did not provide for certain peculiarities of the Indian commercial world such as managing agencies and, therefore, was found to be highly unsatisfactory in several respects in the course of its implementation. Eventually, extensive amendments were introduced by the Indian Companies (Amendment) Act of 1936 (Bhalla 2016, p. 40). The new law also coupled with the Reserve Bank of India founded in 1935.
- [7] See also a very interesting discussion contained in (Simmon 1987). Simmon argues that India saw ‘modern’ industrial development and its relatively buoyant growth rate over the entire inter-war period.
- [8] This article will become relevant to the current debates on economically emergent spatial units “mega regions” in today’s global economy. Mega-regions by definition have large populations, but they also possess large markets, significant economic capacity, substantial innovative activity and highly skilled talent (Florida, Gulden and Mellander 2008). It is assumed that there are one significant mega-regions (“Delhi—Lahore”) and two rapidly expanding regions (“Bangalore—Madras” and “Mumbai—Poona”) in India.

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Analysing changes in Land Surface Temperature using Thermal Remote Sensing technology: A case study of Jamshedpur City, Jharkhand, India

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Abstract: Changes in temperature of a region are resulting from changes in the physical characteristics of the surface, uncontrolled expansion of impervious surfaces, industrialisation and deforestation. The present study is carrying out to quantify the changes happen in temperature of the “Steel City- Jamshedpur” during last 25 years. Jamshedpur is the first planned industrial city of India and due to extensive expansion of industrialization the significant changes have been measured during the study period. It has been also predicted as the 84th fastest growing city in the world for the timeframe 2006–2020 with average annual growth of 2.59%. Landsat data is extensively being used for estimation of temperature in the atmosphere, and thus, this freely available data set provided by NASA helps to understand causes of changing climate at micro scale in the region. This study analyzes the Land Surface Temperature (LST) differences in the study area, and compares with the land use and land cover types using Landsat TM, ETM+ and TIRS data of 1989, 2001 and 2017 respectively. Temperature estimation for Landsat-8 data has been done using Split-Window (SW) algorithm. Results show that the expansion of industrialization leading to impervious surface expansion mostly in the central and southern part of the city. Expansion of industrialization and swapping of vegetation cover in different land cover types has been quantified and visualized in the temperature surface generated from Landsat data. The study reveals temperature increase patterns clustered in patches imitating the surface land use changes and hence warrants strict land use policy formulation and implementation in this fast-growing city of steel.

Keywords: Land Surface Temperature (LST), Split-Window (SW) algorithm, Landsat, Industrialization.

1. Introduction

Uninterrupted monitoring of land surface temperature (LST) and vegetation cover is one of the results of advancement in space technology. Understanding surface temperature variations and Land Use / Land Cover (LU / LC) changes of the Jamshedpur City, Jharkhand, India, is the main objective of this study. Growing population and rapid growth in the industrialization in developing countries is the key issue for global warming and rapid growth in Land Surface Temperature due to heavy combustion from vehicle and emission from impervious surfaces (Hardison et al. 2009; Srivastava et al. 2010; McMillin et al. 1975; Rozenstein et al. 2014).

Geospatial technology has already shown its potential in analyzing Land Surface Temperature and generation of a spatial database for future urban planning and growth assessment. Remote sensing technology provides spatially consistent data sets that cover a large area with high spatial and temporal resolution along with consistent historical time series data for urban change analysis (Weng 2012; Sugg et al. 2014).

A large number of studies have been reported by researchers to identify and monitor the changes in Land Use / Land Cover and its adequate effects in modifying Land Surface Temperature. By applying digital image analysis techniques (Weng 2012; Sugg et al. 2014) and Deng et al. (2012) used multi-temporal LANDSAT TM/ETM images for extraction and assessment of impervious surface areas using spectral unmixing method for Pearl River Delta of China and concluded in their work that multi-temporal satellite images are a very

useful database for calculating the Land Surface Temperature (LST) and Land Use / Land Cover changes.

Various Methods were incorporated already for the retrieval of the LST (Cristobal et al. 2009; Kumar et al. 2012; McMillin 1975; Rozenstein et al. 2014).

Split-Window algorithm is a rapid technique using by multiple scholars around the world to retrieve LST from Landsat 8 TIRS. In the present study the same method has been utilized to analyze the LST.

2. Study Area

Jamshedpur is a large city situated between the Subarnarekha and Kharkai rivers in the east Indian state of Jharkhand. It is located at 22°47'N latitude and 86°12' longitude. Jamshedpur is situated in the southern end of the state of Jharkhand and is bordered by the states of Orissa and West Bengal. The average elevation of the city is 135 metres while it ranges between 129 m to 151 m. Total geographical area of Jamshedpur is ~233 Sq. km. Jamshedpur is primarily located in a hilly region and is surrounded by the Dalma Hills running from west to east and covered with dense forests. Its elevation from sea level is 159 m. It is located in southern part of Chotanagpur Plateau. The summer season falls from March to mid-June, between this range the satellite data were taken, the season of southwest monsoon rains from mid-June to October and cold-weather season from November to February.

Fig. 1. Geographical Location of Study area (Overlay Landsat 8 OLI 2017)

3. Data and Methodology

Landsat Satellite Images (LANDSAT-5 TM, 1989; LANDSAT-7 ETM+, 2001 & LANDSAT-8 OLI/ TIRS, 2017) for Jamshedpur city were utilized for analyzing Land Surface Temperature while calculating the Land Use/Land Cover changes for the same. The detailed methodology is given in Figure no. 02, also the step-by-step description is provided for better understanding.

Land use / land cover maps of the study area for 1989, 2001 and 2017 were generated using unsupervised classification and Iso Cluster & Maximum Likelihood Classification method. As the area is small, therefore, 10 spectral classes were taken for classification and afterward re-classification has been done to extract three spectral classes- Settlements, Vegetation Cover and Water Body. The same pattern of classification was applied on all three-year data. The output maps can be seen in Figure No. 04. The overall accuracy of the classifications was calculated using confusion matrix and the resultant values ranges between 94-97% for the recorded satellite data.

Land surface temperature (LST) was calculated from preprocessed Landsat TM (band 6), Landsat ETM+ (band 6 VCID1) and Landsat TIRS (band 10 & 11). For retrieval of LST from Landsat 5 TM & Landsat 7 ETM+ spectral model was used and for Landsat 8 TIRS split-window method was taken.

Retrieval of LST from Landsat 5 TM & Landsat 7 ETM+

At first, conversion of spectral radiance (L_λ) was done using following equation,

$$L_\lambda = ((LMAX_\lambda - LMIN_\lambda) / (QCALMAX - QCALMIN)) * (QCAL - QCALMIN) + LMIN_\lambda$$

Where, L_λ = Spectral Radiance at the sensor's aperture in watts/ (meter squared*ster* μ m), QCAL = the quantized calibrated pixel value in DN, LMIN $_\lambda$ = the spectral radiance that is scaled to QCALMIN in watts/ (meter squared*ster* μ m), QCALMIN = the minimum quantized calibrated pixel value (corresponding to

LMIN $_\lambda$) in DN, QCALMAX = the maximum quantized calibrated pixel value (corresponding to LMAX $_\lambda$) in DN.

Spectral Radiance (L_λ) to Temperature (K) was calculated using-

$$T = \frac{K2}{\ln\left(\frac{K1}{L_\lambda} + 1\right)}$$

Where, T = effective at satellite temperature in Kelvin, K2 = Calibration constant 2 from table, K1 = Calibration constant 1 from table, L = Spectral radiance in watts/ (meter squared *ster* μ m)

Finally, the retrieved LST in Kelvin converted into degree Celsius-

$$T' = T - 273.15$$

Where, T' = Effective at satellite temperature in Celsius.

Table 1. Thermal Band Calibration Constants for Landsat 5TM and Landsat 7 ETM+

Satellite Data	Constant 1- Watts/(meter squared*ster* μ m)	K1 Constant 2- Kelvin	K2
LANDSAT 5 TM Band 6	607.76	1260.56	
LANDSAT 7 ETM+ Band 6 VCID 1	666.09	1282.71	

(Source: Landsat Science Data Users Handbook, NASA, USA)

Retrieval of LST from Landsat 8 TIRS

Following steps were performed to retrieve LST using Split-Window Algorithm (SW)-

Step 1: Estimation of Top Atmospheric Spectral Radiance (TOAr) was retrieved by converting original digital numbers (DN) values and TIRS into atmospheric radiance. The original DN of Landsat 8 TIR is converted into radiance using-

$$L_\lambda = M_L * Q_{CAL} + A_L$$

Where, L_λ = Spectral radiance (watts / (squared meter * sr* μ m), M_L = Radiance multiplicative scaling factor for the band (RADIANCE_MULT_BAND_n from the metadata), A_L = Radiance additive scaling factor for the band, (RADIANCE_ADD_BAND_n from the metadata), Q_{CAL} = L_1 pixel value in DN

Step 2: Estimation of Brightness Temperature (TB) of Band 10 and 11. Brightness Temperature is the electromagnetic radiation traveling upward from the top

of the Earth’s atmosphere. For both bands TB was calculated (in Degree Celsius) using following formula-

$$T_B = \frac{K_2}{\ln\left(\frac{K_1}{L_\lambda} + 1\right)} - 273.15$$

Where, T_B = effective at satellite temperature in Kelvin, K₂ = Calibration constant 2 from table, K₁ = Calibration constant 1 from table, L = Spectral radiance in watts/ (meter squared *ster*μm)

Table 2. Thermal Constant Values for Landsat 8 TIRS

Thermal Constant	Band 10	Band 11
K ₁	774.89	480.89
K ₂	1321.08	1201.14

(Source: Landsat Science Data Users Handbook, NASA, USA)

Step 3: Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) using OLI sensor optical Band was retrieved using the formula-

$$NDVI = (NIR - Red) / (NIR + Red)$$

Where, NIR = Near Infrared and Red is red band of Optical band.

Step 4: Estimation of proportion of vegetation for calculating emissivity was completed using the formula-

$$P_V = (NDVI - NDVI_{min} / NDVI_{max} - NDVI_{min})^2$$

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Fig. 2. Incorporated Methodological Framework for analyzing Land Surface Temperature using Landsat 5 TM, 7 ETM+ and Landsat 8 OLI / TIRS

Where, P_v = Proportion of Vegetation, NDVI = Normalized Difference Vegetation Index, NDVI_{max} = Maximum value of NDVI, NDVI_{min} = Minimum value of NDVI

Step 5: Emissivity calculation was done using the formula-

$$e = 0.004 * P_V + 0.986$$

Where, e = emissivity, P_v = Proportion of Vegetation

Step 6: Retrieval of LST was done using following Split-Window Algorithm-

$$LST = TB_{10} + C_1(TB_{10} - TB_{11}) + C_2(TB_{10} - TB_{11})^2 + C_0 + (C_3 + C_4W)(1 - \epsilon) + (C_5 + C_6W)\Delta\epsilon$$

Where, LST=Land surface temperature, C₀ – C₆=Split-window coefficient values, TB₁₀ and TB₁₁= Brightness temperature of band 10 and band 11, ε =Mean LSE of TIR bands, Δε = Difference of LSE, W=Atmospheric water vapor content (0.01 for the Jamshedpur, taken from secondary sources).

Fig. 3. NDVI for 1989, 2001 & 2017

Table 3. Split-Window coefficients value

Constant	Value
C0	-0.268
C1	1.378
C2	0.183
C3	54.3
C4	-2.238
C5	-129.2
C6	16.4

(Source: Skokovic et al, 2014; Sobrino et al, 1996; 2003; Shaouhua Zhao et al, 2009)

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 NDVI

Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) is used to determine the density of greenness on a patch of land. The pigment in plant leaves, chlorophyll, strongly absorbs visible light (from 0.4 to 0.7 μm) for use in photosynthesis. The cell structure of the leaves, on the other hand, strongly reflects near-infrared light (from 0.7 to 1.1 μm).

In the present study for the year 1989, about >60% vegetation's NDVI was found ranging 0.40 to 0.60 (healthy vegetation). While for 2001 it decreased upto 50% and for 2017 it diminished to ~45%. It shows that the health of the vegetation decreased due to rapid expansion of heavy industrialization. Figure No. 03 explains the status of NDVI for all three years 1989, 2001 and 2017.

4.2 Land Use / Land Cover Analysis

Detailed figures of calculated areas with respective to takes classes are given in Table no. 04 & 05. The area for settlements was increased by 126.5 % from 1989 (33.63 sq.km.) to 2001 (76.21 sq.km.) while from 1989 to 2017 (122.48 sq.km.) the changes have been recorded 264.14%. Figure No. 04 illustrates the growth in settlements from 1989 to 2017.

Due to heavy industrialization the population and the respective settlements were increased enormously.

Table 4. Land Use / Land Cover area (in sq. km.) for study period

LU/LC Class	1989	2001	2017
(Area- in sq. km.)			
Water Body	11.09	11.87	15.11
Settlements	33.63	76.21	122.48
Vegetation	32.35	22.19	36.56
Bare Soil	156.06	122.85	58.97
Total	233.13	233.13	233.13

Table 5. Land Use / Land Cover area (in %age) with respect to Table 4

LU/LC Class	1989	2001	2017
(%age of total area)			
Water Body	4.76	5.09	6.48
Settlements	14.43	32.69	52.54
Vegetation	13.87	9.52	15.68
Bare Soil	66.94	52.69	25.29
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Fig. 4. LU / LC graph for study period

Fig. 5. LU / LC Maps for 1989, 2001 & 2017

4.3 Land Surface Temperature

From LST calculation it was found that the area lies between 40–45 °C is increased from 35 sq.km (1989) to ~160 sq.km. (2017). Almost ~350% change in the high temperature range (40–45 °C) is found. Generated maps for the study years 1989, 2001 & 2017 may be seen in Figure No. 06. The temperature bar 25–30 °C for the area lie in 1989 has been shifted to bar 30–35 °C for the same area lie in 2017. In settlements class, changes in temperature found enormous due to rapid expansion of industrial area.

Fig. 6. Land Surface Temperature using for 1989, 2001 & 2017 using Landsat-5 TM, Landsat-7 ETM+ and Landsat 8 OLI / TIRS satellite images

5. Conclusion

The present study reveals the radical changes in Land Use / Land Cover area as well as in Land Surface Temperature. The changes in Land Use / Land Cover changed the radiant surface temperature and consequently surface energy budget. The diminishing health of vegetation, resultant NDVI calculation, also illustrates the increasing trend in LST from 1989 to 2017. The heavy expansion of industrialization in the Northern and Eastern parts, from the central zone of the study area can be easily seen from the LU / LC maps from 1989 to 2017. Expansion in industrialization triggered to rapid growth in the population which lead to the expansion in the built-up area of the Jamshedpur. The rapid growth in the settlements and removal of vegetation for industrialization affected the LST at large scale in the study area. Thus, increase in LST and decrease in NDVI reveals the current status of both variables for “Steel City- Jamshedpur”.

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Past is the key to the future: Landslide Inventory

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Abstract: Results driving from an archival and bibliographical research are here presented, concerning the landslides occurred in Ranikhola river basin, Sikkim, India. More than 74.41% of landslide information was extracted from existing Geological Survey of India report, PhD thesis, archive and scientific publication. Special attention was paid to triggering factors, which resulted to be essentially rainfall and human activity. Finally, reported landslides in the given sources as being induced by rainfall from 1969-2017, were preliminary analyzed, with the aim of verifying the reliability of information gathered from the sources. The quality of the information gathered from the different sources is not homogeneous. The highest quality rank is held by GSI report and scientific publications which generally allowed fill gaps in all the databases fields. On the contrary, the available PhD thesis contains very concise information but date is often missing.

Keywords: Landslide inventory, Ranikhola river basin, Sikkim, India.

1. Introduction

According to Guzzetti et al. (2012) landslide inventory is “the simplest of landslide mapping is a landslide inventory, which records the spatial location, time and date of occurrence, type of landslide movement that leave the visible traces in the area”. Landslide inventory map is key essential point for studying the relationship among the conditioning factors and landslide event. These are the base for analyzing landslide susceptibility, hazard and risk (Dai and Lee, 2008; van Westen et al., 2008). Landslide inventory are essential for landslide susceptibility models that predict landslide on the basis of past conditions. If the inventory is not sufficiently available more emphasis should be given on expert assessment and evaluation. Therefore, we need to know where landslides happened in the past. Historical inventories have very much important as the smaller landslides has been lost due to various degrees of modification by subsequent landslides, erosional processes, vegetation growth and anthropogenic activities.

Thus, it needs to collect the historical reports/data and prepare landslide inventory map to overcome the consequences of landslide. Landslide inventory has a great importance as it provides important information to decision makers/planners and constitute basic information for landslide susceptibility, hazard and risk analysis.

1.1 Study area

The present study is a part of Sikkim Lesser Himalayas and falls in the drainage basin of Rani Khola River and is bounded by the geographical coordinates of 27° 14' N, 88° 29' E and 27° 23' N, 88° 43' E respectively (Fig. 1). Rani Khola drainage basin is the sub-basin of Tista valley and its land use potential in East Sikkim having a geographical area of 249 sq km. The study area is the interfluvial of many rivers and rivulets (Chakraborty and Hait 2014). The Rani Khola drainage basin have importance of physical and cultural point of

view as it sustains the hill cities and towns namely Gangtok, Ranipool, Rumtek, Singtam, Tadong, Bhusuk etc. The study area is the hub of all administrative activity of the Sikkim state. An isohyatal data analysis reveals that ‘South-East quadrant’ (Mangan, Singhik, Dikchu, Gangtok, Rongli etc) experiences maximum rainfall. The month of July is the wettest month in the area (Fig. 2). The annual average rainfall is 3500mm at Gangtok city, which is the Capital of Sikkim state (Bhasin et al. 2002). The region falls under subtropical highland climate class according to Koppen’s classification of climate scheme. The climate of the study area is characterized by cool and humid with 27.5°C maximum and 1.5°C minimum temperature. According to hazard map of the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), Sikkim state falls under high zone of landslide hazard (Kaur et al. 2018). Due to its geoenvironmental characteristics the area is prone to frequent landslide, earthquake, flood and windstorm hazards (Kaur et al. 2018). The main reasons for landslide occurrences in the basin are due to the geology of the area combined with heavy rainfall (Mehrotra et al. 1996). Sometimes natural phenomenon like earthquake and flood also induce numerous landslides in the Rani Khola River basin. In the past, the region witnessed major floods in 1960, 1971, 1973, 2012, 2016 and earthquake in 2011 which triggered a series of a landslide in the Tista valley. Recurring landslides and slope failures in the area has caused destruction to communication of corridors, roads, agricultural land, loss of human life and properties (Kaur et al. 2017a). Moreover, the nature (state, activity & style), type (material involved & movement), intensity and distribution of landslides and related phenomenon across the region are highly variable.

1.2 Geology of the study area

The study area is the part of eastern Himalayas and covered by mostly Precambrian rocks consisting of five geological Formations namely (i) Kanchenjunga Formation, (ii) Darjeeling Formation, (iii) Chunthang Formation, (iv) Everest Pelitic Formation and (v) Daling Formation (Table 1). Quaternary deposits of alluvium are

sporadically developed along rivers and streams. Numerous thrusts, faults, joints, folds etc have developed in the rocks due to structural disturbance. The area is

Age	Formation	Group	Lithology
Early Palaeozoic	Daling Formation	Rabung Group	Phyllites, Slates
Pre-Cambrian	Everest Pelitic Formation		Phyllites, and Phyllitic quartzites, Quartz-biotite Schist
Pre-Cambrian	Rongli Schist Formation	Sikkim Group	Silvery mica-schist, Stauroilite bearing biotite schist
	Darjeeling Gneiss Formation		Garnet-biotite gneiss, Kynaite and sillimanite bearing gneiss, Coarse grained biotite-gneiss
-----CHUNGTHUNG THRUST-----			
Pre-Cambrian	Chungthung Formation		Massive quartzites and Flaggy quartzites
-----MAIN CENTRAL THRUST-----			
Pre-Cambrian	Kanchenjunga Gneiss Formation		Augen gneiss and Banded gneiss

traversed by Main Central Thrust (MCT) and Chungthang Thrust. MCT trending NE-SE is characterized with Kanchenjunga Gneiss Formation and Chungthang Formation. Chungthang Thrust also trending NW-SE involves Chungthang Formation (Gneiss) and Sikkim group (Schist).

Table 1. Techno-stratigraphy of the study area (Raina and Srivastava, 1981)

2. Methodology

2.1 Data collection

The historical research started with the analysis of existing Geological Survey of India (GSI) reports and archives focused on landslide events. They were:

- Landslide compendium on Darjeeling Sikkim Himalayas (Geological Survey of India, 2016)
- Archive of DST project (Yudhbir and Gergan, 2004)
- PhD thesis (Kalita, 2006)
- Local newspapers (Sikkim express, Himali Bela)

GSI carried out a nationwide inventory on landslides. Eventually, they proceeded with field-checks, surveying, landslide morphology study, and large scale geological mapping which were documented.

2.2 Preparation of landslide inventory map

Landslide inventory or distribution map is prepared to determine the landslide affected area (%) and density of landslides for each subclass of landslide conditioning factors (Mondal and Maiti, 2013). Generally, two types of inventory are namely landslide inventory map (Basharat et al. 2016; Kaur et al. 2018; Gupta et al. 2018) and event landslide inventory map (Guzzetti et al. 2012; Mondini et al. 2014). Landslide inventory map shows the location and spatial extent whereas event landslide inventory indicates the extent, location, and typology of landslide hazard caused by triggering factors. High accuracy/resolution spatial data plays a crucial role (Jebur et al. 2013) in developing landslide inventory. Landslide inventory mapping for the past 50 years (1966-2016) indicates that there are four major types of landslide in the study area namely; debris slide, debris fall, rock slide, and rock fall. In this study landslide inventory is prepared from high-resolution data like Resourcesat-2 (LISS IV Mx), Google Earth and GSI reported data. Several field surveys are conducted to identify the landslide area as well as cross check the prepared landslide location form satellite data. A total of 256 landslide data have been taken as landslide inventory (185 landslides are rainfall induced, 13 landslides are related to earthquake, 9 landslides are related to anthropogenic activity, and 49 data has missing the source of triggering factor) (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Study area map

Fig. 2. Spatial location of landslide with special reference to triggering factors

3. Results

The research led to find out 228 records which corresponds to 256 landslides occurred in the time span of 1957-2016. The overall distribution of records among the various sources is shown Fig. 3, where is evident that newspapers provided about 12.60% of information collected. GSI and PhD Thesis records provided 28.35% information for landslides data. The historical collection of inventory data of landslides from newspaper can be consulted at two local newspaper agencies of Sikkim State namely Sikkim express founded in 1976 (English newspaper) and Himali Bela founded in 1977 (Nepali newspaper). After completing the re-examination of the records displayed in Archive of the newspaper agencies, a further research was performed, aimed at covering the time interval from 1976 – 2016. Some other valuable information was extracted from scientific papers, PhD thesis, and reported Geological Survey of India (GSI) data (Figure), even though Ranikhola river basin were dealt with in very few cases. In fact, the study area faced more landslides in the past but few of them were reported. The result of the research carried out regional rainfall-induced landslides over the Ranikhola river basin, Sikkim.

The records were eventually organized in a database, consisting of the following fields: triggering factors, data, place, movement, type, and sources. A landslide inventory map was compiled (Fig. 2).

Fig. 3. Distribution of records in the examined sources.

Temporal distribution of the 256 landslides is shown in histogram (Fig. 4). The main peak corresponds to 2011 (Fig. 4), due to major rainfall-induced landslide episode and 2011 Sikkim earthquake which occurred in September and caused a high number of landslides in whole the region. The average annual rainfall for 2011 was 3402.7mm.

Fig. 4. Annual distribution of landslides for the periode 1957-2016

3.1 Relation between landslide occurrences and rainfall

To measures landslide critical value of rainfall probability in the study area, hourly rainfall data from 1969-2017 collected from Indian meteorological department (IMD). Analysis of rainfall data from June to September (Monsoon period) showed that highest rainfall 222.5 mm occurred on 08July, 1997, with cumulative rainfall of 3-day period was 418mm. Rainfall across whole the study area was same as the study area has single weather station which was then considered with respect to landslide occurrences. The data were analyzed in terms of date and location of the landslide, the nature of the landslide and the area which it occurred, and meteorological data available from the local station. In Fig. 5, the horizontal (X) axis indicates cumulative rainfall for 1, 3 and 5 days before day of landslide occurrence and vertical (Y) axis represents rainfall on the day of landslide. Landslides were considered to be triggered by rainfall on the day of occurrence when data plotted to a region under 1:1 curve.

Fig. 5 represents that rainfall on the day of the landslide and cumulative rainfall of 1, 3, and 5 days respectively. In Fig. 5a compares rainfall on the landslide day with cumulative rainfall for one day which indicates that more landslides are plotted over the border (30 data points) and 15 points under the equi- line of 1:1 curve, indicating that these landslides were mainly caused by rainfall on the day. It was observed that the data points were evenly distributed in 1:1 curve (15 data points over the border and 18 points under the border), indicating that landslides were generated equally by rainfall on the day and three days cumulative rainfall (Fig. 5b). As seen in Fig. 5c rainfall on the day of landslide and cumulative rainfall for five days before the landslide, shows that more landslides data points plotted to area under rather than over the equi-line of 1:1 curve (15 data points are over the borderline and 30 points are under the curve), indicates that landslides were occurred due to five day cumulative rainfall, rather than by rainfall on the day of occurrence.

Fig. 5 (a) One-day cumulative rainfall before the failure day (b) Three-day cumulative rainfall before the failure day (c) five-day cumulative rainfall before the failure day

4. Discussion and Conclusion

The quality of the information gathered from the different sources is not homogeneous. The highest quality rank is held by GSI report and scientific publications which generally allowed fill in all the databases fields. On the contrary, the available PhD thesis contains very concise information but date is often missing. The role of rainfall as landslide triggering factors is confirmed by antecedent rainfall relation (Fig. 5).

In conclusion, it can be stated that the research so far performed gave useful and interesting results concerning the landslide susceptibility of the Ranikhola river basin. The historical information showed that most of all the landslides phenomena were induced by rainfall. The research on landslide susceptibility of Ranikhola river basin is still ongoing, aiming at several goals as i) completing the examination of newspapers going back until 80s ii) analyzing more in detail the antecedent rainfall data, in view of possible relationship among some parameters (duration, intensity, mean annual rainfall etc iii) performing a closer comparison between historical and recent landslides iv) preparing a landslide hazard map.

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The relationship between urban formation of colonial Saigon City and Vietnamese people: An analysis of land ownership and the change in city boundary

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Abstract: This study maps the changes in land ownership by race in Saigon City during the colonial period (1865–1908). Through an analysis of the legal situation and a comparative analysis of the transfer of land ownership between certain sections of the land register map, the following conclusions were reached: (1) the legal system (orders and decrees) in the early colonial period had double standards; in the inner parts of the city, the public land disposal system was open to all races, while in the peripheral part of the city the colonial government designated settlements for the Vietnamese. (2) Despite having possessed land in the central part of the city during the early colonial period, many Vietnamese sold their land because of the land speculation boom of the late nineteenth century. They later sold their land on the peripheries of the city too. These processes led to the lowering of the proportion of land owned by the Vietnamese. (3) Meanwhile, on the peripheries of the city, Vietnamese landholdings continued until the beginning of the twentieth century. The distribution of settlements and the active resale of land by the Vietnamese were the main causes for the uneven distribution of land between races.

Keywords: Concession, Saigon, indigenous people, land register map.

1. Introduction

This article attempts to explore the relationship between the urban formation of colonial Saigon City and the Vietnamese people from the mid-nineteenth to the early twentieth century via an analysis of ethnic patterns of land ownership and changes in the city's boundary in colonial-era Saigon ^[1].

Saigon was an archetypal colonial city built at the center of what is today Ho Chi Minh City, which served as the capital of Cochinchina, a French colony encompassing southern Vietnam. It was the first area of residence for French colonists in Vietnam, for Cochinchina was occupied at the earliest stage of the French colonization of Vietnam and ruled directly by the French. In 1890, of the 2,381 French citizens, excluding the military, living in Cochinchina, 1,492, or around 62%, were residents of Saigon (*AIF*. 1890 v.1: 547). The situation remained similar into the early twentieth century for in 1921, 6,179 of the 10,086 French citizens in Cochinchina, roughly 61% were Saigon residents (*ASI*. 1913 1922: 36–37). Saigon had the strong feature of “a colony in the colony (*une colonie dans la colonie*)” (Pretini 1992: 92). However, such a characteristic did not necessarily apply to other cities in Vietnam. For example, in 1914, 6,487 Europeans resided in Saigon, as indicated in the yearbook. On the other hand, Hanoi, which was a capital in the Indochinese Federation, had only 2,700 Europeans. Haiphong, the greatest trading port in northern Vietnam, had 1,714 Europeans in its population (Table 1) ^[2].

The idea that Saigon was a residential hub for French colonists is clearly indicated by both its urban planning and its legal situation. The idea behind the town, as depicted in the first plans for the city drawn up by

Lieutenant Colonel Paul Coffyn of the Marine Engineering Corps Roads and Bridges Department in 1862, was to make Saigon “one European city” (*une ville Européenne*) (Bouchot 1927: 38). With regard to its legal position, Saigon held a status similar to cities in France, and was the only city in Indochina with the right of autonomous governance. For example, the municipal organization of the city in 1877 was based on French municipal organization laws (*BOCF*. 1877, No.77: 128–155) ^[3]. The authorities of the Indochinese Federation expressed this status that “Authority (of the city of Saigon) was the same as it of the city of France, and the only difference (between the city of Saigon and cities in France) is that the municipal council includes four indigenous members” (*AGI*. Commercial, industriel, administratif 1914: 436).

If one particular feature of Saigon during this period was that it was politically structured as a French town, a second was the economic dominance of immigrants from Asia, and the Chinese in particular. First, in the early days of the construction of colonial Saigon City, Chinese merchants immigrated from Singapore made an important contribution to urban construction. One such well-known Chinese merchant was Wang-tai, who ran a hotel in which the office of the Saigon municipal committee was based in the early days of French colonization ^[4]. Second, as is well known, from the founding of the port in 1860, Saigon became the place from which Cochinchina's primary product, rice from the Mekong Delta, was exported (Kikuchi 1988). The rice distribution chain was monopolized by Chinese merchants, and almost all of the rice for export was polished in the Chinese town of Chợ Lớn (Coquerel 1911: 115), located 5 km west of the center of Saigon City. Because of this economic structure, the Chinese came to monopolize the retail trade within Saigon. Moreover, the

overseas Chinese overwhelmed the Vietnamese in the fields of the distribution industry or retail trade. For example, in 1894, Catinat street, the main business street of Saigon City, was occupied by dress-and-ornaments clothing stores, jewelers, tailors, bookstores, grocery stores, beauty parlors, watch stores, and printing offices managed by the French, and laundries, shoe stores, ornament stores, and tailors managed by the Chinese (Indochine française 1894: 187).

Table 1. Ethnic makeup in main cities
in Vietnam and Cambodia (1914)

	Europeans	Chinese	Indians	Vietnamese	Cambodians	Others	Total
Saigon City							
population	6,487	21,739	1,549	35,576	89	702	66,142
ratio	9.80%	32.87%	2.34%	53.80%	0.13%	1.06%	100.00%
Cholon City							
population	419	80,120 ⁽¹⁾	54	87,057	115	22	167,787
ratio	0.20%	44.80%	0.00%	51.90%	0.07%	3.00%	100.00%
Tourane City							
population	235	598	15	7,000	N/A	10	7,858
ratio	2.99%	7.61%	0.19%	89.08%	N/A	0.13%	100.00%
Hanoi City⁽²⁾							
population	2,700	2,041	75	80,000	N/A	72	84,888
ratio	3.20%	2.40%	0.10%	94.20%	N/A	0.10%	100.00%
Haiphong City							
population	1,714	9,855	48	35,000 ⁽³⁾	N/A	422	47,039
ratio	3.60%	21.00%	0.10%	74.40%	N/A	0.90%	100.00%
Phnom-Penh City							
population	696	18,655	387	15,452	30,385	141	65,716
ratio	1.06%	28.39%	0.59%	23.51%	46.24%	0.21%	100.00%

(Source: AGI. Partie administrative 1914: 358, 362, 447, 457, 529)

Notes: (1) Includes 4,873 Minh Hường people. The Minh Hường were originally an ethnic group whose ancestors immigrated from China during the transition period between the Ming and Qing dynasties. In the nineteenth century, the Minh Hường were classed as Vietnamese by a decree on December 7, 1869 and a decision on August 31, 1874, but after November 13, 1909, the Minh Hường were classified as Chinese (*Recueil des instructions, circulaires et avis concernant le service judiciaire de l'Indo-Chine. Supplément 1909*: 176). (2) Excludes suburban zone (*zone suburbaine*). (3) Includes all indigenous peoples (*Indigènes*).

Indians were another ethnic group whose economic interest was opposed to that of the Vietnamese. From the beginnings of the French conquest of Cochinchina, many “renouncers” (Indians who were legally recognized as French citizens) from French India were employed in the Cochinchinese administration, and Indians, especially Chettiars, actively invested in urban property as soon as their arrival in the colonies in the 1870s (Pairaudeau 2016: 4–8, 106).

The economic dominance of these Asian immigrants led to the anti-Chinese and anti-Indian boycotts by Vietnamese nationalist groups from the 1900s (Pairaudeau 2016: 216–217) (Peycam 2012: 80–

92). One of the subject matters of the anti-Chinese and anti-Indian boycotts was the accumulation of land by Asian immigrants. For example, *Công Luận (Opinion)*, a popular Quốc Ngữ newspaper published in Saigon City, reported that “One half of the land of Saigon City was bought by them (Chinese)” or “The capital of Cholon province (Cholon City) did not by any means belong to the Vietnam (*đất nước Annam*) (*Công Luận* 1922/07/21: 1)”^[5].

Then what was the background to this accumulation of land by Asian immigrants in Saigon? An explosion of papers argued about the economic dominance of these Asian immigrants in Southern Vietnam. However, few studies have targeted the real process of land accumulation by Asian immigrants. In order to begin addressing this question, we should look at policy, especially land policies of the French colonial authority on the indigenous people. In this context, Section 1 examines the position that the Vietnamese were placed in by the process of the creation of a French colonial city by comparing the changes of Saigon City’s zoning from the mid-nineteenth to the early twentieth century with the locations of Vietnamese residences created by the French colonial authority. Then, Section 2 demonstrates how the Vietnamese responded to these land policies introduced by their colonizers. by analyzing the long-term transformation in ethnic makeup of landholders in certain districts of the city.

2. The Vietnamese and the creation of a French colonial city: Municipal boundary lines and the establishment of settlements

The concession system was introduced to colonial Cochinchina as a system of distribution for those who wanted public land (state land) that either had no recorded owner or had been created by canal construction, and gave the owner’s permission to develop it (Takada 2014, 30) (*BOCF*. 1865, No.39: 50–51)^[6]. Upon colonization, in order to implement this system of disbursing land, all landholdings within the city were confiscated by the French, and the indigenous people’s rights to land that they held in Saigon were entirely rendered null and void (*BOEC*. 1862, No.44: 91–93) (*BOCF*. 1865, No.120: 176) (*BOCF*. 1865, No.78: 85–87). The indigenous people of Saigon are nearly synonymous with Vietnamese, as the populations of Cambodians, Laotians and other indigenous Indochina peoples were very small and had almost no economic power^[7].

A particular feature of French rule emphasized in previous studies is that indigenous people were allowed to participate in this system of disbursing public land, and superficially there was no zoning of residential districts by ethnicity (Wright 1991: 222–223). This argument is based on the fact that the system of disbursing public land during the early years of colonial Saigon incorporated Vietnamese landowners, and the Vietnamese who

converted to Catholicism were allowed to reside in Saigon irrespective of wealth (Tainturier 2004: 71–77) (Vo 2011: 76). In fact, as the system for disbursing public land did not specify ethnic criteria, it was possible for the Vietnamese to acquire land in Saigon through this concession system. However, as various pieces of legislation instituting the system for disbursing public land were introduced, it became clear in stipulations relating to the land ownership and residences of the Vietnamese that France sought to clearly demarcate separate spaces for the French (and Europeans) and the Vietnamese. To test this hypothesis, first, I would like to identify changes in the city's zoning from the mid-nineteenth century to the early twentieth century, and second, I would like to identify the location of the residences of the Vietnamese.

2.1 The changes in Saigon City's zoning

At the beginning of the nineteenth century, that is, just before colonization, the center of today's Ho Chi Minh City had two nuclei (Fig. 1). One was the area on the right bank of Saigon River, surrounded by the Thị Nghè and Bến Nghé canals [8]. In this area, in 1790, Nguyễn Phúc Ánh (Emperor Gia Long, the first Emperor of the Nguyễn dynasty) constructed the Gia Định citadel (嘉定城), a Vauban-styled fortification, as a base from which to rule southern Vietnam. Surrounding the citadel was the Vietnamese political and commercial quarter [9]. I would like to refer to the area around the citadel as the Gia Định citadel area. Another nucleus was a Chinatown called the Sài Gòn phố (柴棍舖, now Chợ Lớn area) area, located around 5 km west from along Bến Nghé canal. "Sài Gòn phố" was the biggest Chinatown in Vietnam, formed after a large-scale Chinese immigration in 1778.

Therefore, after the conquest, how did the colonial authority decide on the domain of Saigon City as the capital of Cochinchina? The first decree (on April 1, 1861) regarding the domain of Saigon City determined that this was the area that was surrounded by three waterways, the Bến Nghé canal, the Saigon river, and the Thị Nghè canal, and the line that connects ancient Cay-mai pagoda and Ki-Hoa (Bouchot 1927: 37–38), the line that connects ancient Cay-mai pagoda and Ki-Hoa equivalent to earthworks ("旧壘" on Fig. 1) of the 1772 construction. In short, this area included two nuclei of the Nguyễn period, the Gia Định citadel and the "Sài Gòn (now Chợ Lớn)" areas. Lieutenant Colonel Paul Coffyn, who drew up the first plans for the city, insisted that the Bến Nghé and Thị Nghè canals should be connected by excavation, and therefore "All sides of Saigon should be surrounded by water, and Saigon should be a genuine island (*véritable îlot*)" (Bouchot 1927: 37). This setting of municipal boundary suggests that at the time the French colonists intended to defend the colonial city from local society by waterways (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Center of today's Ho Chi Minh City in the Nguyễn period

(Source: Author's own)

However, in just over four years (in 1865), the surface of Saigon City significantly decreased, and a new city boundary was marked off only around the area of the Gia Định citadel and the Vietnamese commercial quarter [10]. In the existing document the reason cited by the colonial government to change the boundary of Saigon City is not clear. Provably thinking, Coffyn's plan, that assumed that the population of Saigon City was 500,000–600,000 and that the gross area of the city was 2,500 ha (Bouchot 1927: 38), as Nguyễn Đình Đầu pointed out, was impossible to realize, because the domain of Saigon City decided in 1861 was too large to control for newborn colonial authority (Nguyễn Đình Đầu 1998a: 79). Anyway, it is likely that they changed their city planning policy so that the city territory was the area that they practiced city planning, as the new city territory matched the area that already had grid pattern roads in 1865. This new territory fixed in 1865 (the surface of which was approximately 448 ha) remained for around 30 years, until 1894. Its architecture symbolized colonial power, for example, Saigon central post office, Notre-Dame Cathedral Basilica of Saigon, Palace of the Governor General, the city opera house, were all distributed in the area [11]. From the end of the nineteenth century to the beginning of the twentieth, the territory started to expand (Fig. 3).

Fig. 2. Coffyn’s plan in 1862

(Source: Bouchot 1927: np.)

The first expansion of Saigon City was undertaken in 1894 when villages situated on the right bank of the Thị Nghè canal (villages of Hoà My, Phú Hoà, Nam Chon, Tân Định and a part of the village of X(H)uan Hoà) were annexed to Saigon City (BOIF. 1894, No. 575: 955) (Baudrait 1936b: 40–42). Soon thereafter, in 1895, the area on the right bank of the Bến Nghé canal, a part of the village of Khánh Hội and Tân Hội, was annexed to Saigon City (BOIF. 1895, No. 125: 199) (Baudrait 1936b: 301–302). The third expansion was in 1904, when the villages of Phú Thạnh of Gia Định Province and Tân Hoà of Chợ Lớn province, situated in the area between Saigon City and Cholon City were annexed to Saigon City (or Cholon City) (Baudrait 1936b: 301–303) (LTQG2. Domaines. 6795) ^[12]. After 1904, the city territory was not drastically changed at least until the end of the colonial era.

2.2 The changes in Saigon City’s zoning

Now then, where did the colonial authority locate the residences for the Vietnamese? In 1862, the colonial administration decided to distribute land in an area on the right bank of the Bến Nghé Canal to former city landowners (Bouchot 1927: 341). This area of distribution was located outside Saigon in the village of Tứ Xuân^[13].

Fig. 3. Changes in the city’s zoning from 1862 to 1967

(Source: Author’s own)

At this time, the French also established settlements for the Vietnamese outside the city. Settlements for the Vietnamese were located in two areas (Fig. 4). One area was that between the northwest corner of the former Gia Định citadel (constructed by Minh Mạng) and the Thị Nghè canal. The elevation of this area was around 2–4 meters, and thus it was a comparably high and dry area^[14]. The French colonial authority decided to establish settlements in three villages named Hiep Hoà, Phu Hoà, and An Hoà, for the Vietnamese who had emigrated from Đà Nẵng, a major city in central Vietnam, together with the French army (BOEC. 1862, No.91: 150–151) (Nguyễn Nghị 2007: 147–148). Many Christians resided in these villages (today known as the Tân Định-Đakao area), and in 1863 and 1864 the French colonial authority gave land and money to the Vietnamese in these villages for the construction of a church (BOEC. 1864, No.1: 2) (BOEC. 1864, No.19: 25). The fact that after colonization the French colonial authority promoted Vietnamese Christians is well known (Chesneaux [1955]: 115–116). These three villages were assumed to be settlements of Vietnamese Christians, and in this area a settlement for refugees who did not belong to any village was also established (BOEC. 1864, No.61: 82) ^[15].

Fig. 4. Vietnamese residential areas around Saigon in the 1860s

(Source: Author's own)

Another area was that located between Cầu Kho canal and Chợ Quán, roughly speaking the area between Saigon City and Cholon City. This area was low land with an elevation of only around one meter. The Cầu Kho Chợ Quán areas were old settlements of Vietnamese existing since the Nguyễn Dynasty [16]. In 1864, all the lands in this area were dispersed to the Vietnamese habitants of five villages: Tân Hoà, Phuoc Hung, Nhon Giang, Binh Yên, Tân Quan, and Tân Thanh (BOEC. 1864, No.51: 70) [17].

The distribution of these settlements and a comparison of changes to Saigon City's zoning from 1865 to 1903 shows that until 1893, the French were clearly seeking to demarcate French (and European) spaces from the Vietnamese (refer to previously listed Fig. 3 and Fig. 4). In sum, for the Vietnamese, the system for disbursing public land by exchanging their land in the city for allotments outside it became the formal means by which they were geographically excluded from the city.

From this section, the following conclusions can be drawn: (1) The central pillar in the French establishment of the city was the system for disbursing public land, and inclusion in this system was not dependent upon ethnicity. (2) At the same time, ethnic separation was achieved through the establishment of settlements. Thus, legislation during the early colonial period was contradictory.

3. The Vietnamese and the creation of a French colonial city: Municipal boundary lines and the establishment of settlements

How did the Vietnamese respond to these land policies introduced by their colonizers? This section will highlight Vietnamese attitudes toward the French redistribution of land by analyzing the long-term transformation in the ethnic makeup of landholders in certain districts of the city.

3.1 Segregation in urban and rural areas

In the latter half of the first decade of the twentieth century, the municipal office of Saigon undertook a large-scale expropriation of land around what is now Bến Thành Market (central market of the Saigon area) so that Trans-Indochina Railroad's Saigon station could be moved and an avenue built connecting Saigon City and Cholon City (Boulevard Saigon-Cholon) [18]. The French colonial government of Cochinchina announced this to landowners in four stages: In the first stage (1), the Quoc Ngu Gazette "*Gia Định Báo* (嘉定報)" (Quoc Ngu is a Vietnamese Latin-derived script) notified in both Quoc Ngu and Chinese on June 3, 1907 that the expropriation of land would begin in recent years (*Gia Định Báo* 1907/06/03: np.). In the second stage (2), the Quoc Ngu Gazette notified in both Quoc Ngu and Chinese on August 3, 1908 that the expropriation of land would begin in recent years (*Gia Định Báo* 1908/08/03: np.). In the third stage [19], an investigation into the origins of land ownership and property transfers between 1865 and 1908 (the expropriation survey) was undertaken in 1908 in relevant districts (LTQG2. Domaines: 10579). In the fourth stage (4), the Quoc Ngu Gazette notified in Chinese on January 4, 1909 that the expropriation of land would begin in recent years (*Gia Định Báo* 1909/01/04: np.) (Table 2). To this author's knowledge, there are no historical records of the cadastral situation in Saigon as a whole. Therefore, the materials that allow verification of this expropriation are vital for analyzing property relations in colonial-era Saigon. The analysis in this section is based on the four above-mentioned sources.

Table 2. Four stages of announcement by the Cochinchina government about land expropriation

	Languages	Sources
1st. stage	Quốc Ngữ / Chinese	<i>Gia Định Báo</i> 1907/06/03
2nd. stage	Quốc Ngữ / Chinese	<i>Gia Định Báo</i> 1908/08/03
3rd. stage	French	LTQG2. Domaines 10579
4th. stage	Chinese	<i>Gia Định Báo</i> 1909/01/04

(Source: Author's own)

From a contemporary cadastral map, it is clear that Section A is a district that had been a part of Saigon since its founding, and therefore had its land distributed through the public land disposal system. Section F was an area incorporated into Saigon in 1894, and Section H was an area incorporated in 1904. Therefore, sections F and H were outside the city from the time Saigon was established to 1904 and were peripheral areas of the city thereafter [20].

In terms of geographical features, Section A was an uninhabited, marshy area in the 1860s that was exploited in the late nineteenth century. The 1867 map of Section A indicates that it was a marshland through which canals flowed and thus where people do not live (ANOM. 2PL: 719). On the 1878 map, this marshland had changed to a

swamp called “*Marais Boresse*” (Fig. 5). On the map of 1895 and 1898 “*Marais Boresse*” disappears because of reclamation (Fig. 6) (BNF. GE: 2682). These changes indicate that Section A was originally a marshland; after colonialization, soil was drained off and a swamp formed; then from 1878 to 1895 the swamp was reclaimed and new roads were constructed. On the other hand, changes in large geographical features are not seen in Section H in the topography map of 1900 (ANOM. 1PL. 1362. NO3) and the pictorial map drawn in 1815 (the pre-colonial era). In 1898, Section H was a suburban farming area, where rice, and areca, and coconut palm trees were cultivated.

Fig. 5. Section A on the topography map drawn in 1878
(Source: BNF. GED. 3642, gallica.bnf.fr / BnF)

Fig. 6. Sections A and H on the topography map drawn in 1895
(Source: BNF. GE C-2144, gallica.bnf.fr / BnF)

Fig. 7 aggregates the (assumed) ethnicity of landowners of the 138 plots which were to be expropriated in 1909 (refer fourth stage in the previous paragraph), and the locations (sections or streets) on the land cadastral map that were recorded [21]. As the size of the plots is not clear, the aggregation is not on the basis of area (size) but on the number of plots. In Section A, the

Vietnamese held 14 plots (23.7% of the total number of plots), while the Indians held 13 plots (22.0%), the Chinese 10 (16.9%) and Europeans 8 (13.6%). This shows that, even in the center of Saigon, Vietnamese did hold land, and Indians and Chinese both held significant proportions too, while the proportion held by Europeans was lower. By contrast, in Section H, the proportion of land (plots) held by Vietnamese was as high as 59.5% (50 plots), with Europeans 10.7% (9 plots), the Paris Foreign Missions Society (*Missions Étrangères de Paris*) holding 9.5% (8 plots), the Chinese 3.6 % (3 plots), and Indians 2.4 % (2 plots).

Fig. 7. Ethnicity of landowners of the 141 plots to be expropriated (in 1909)

(Source: LTQG2. Domaines: 10579, *Gia Định Báo* 1908/08/03: np., *Gia Định Báo* 1909/01/04: np.)

Hence, from Fig. 7 we can see that there was a clear distinction between the ethnic composition of landowners between Section A, which had been within the city when it was founded, and Section H, which fell outside city limits (meaning that segregation was by section). Despite this, the ethnic composition of landowners in both sections was diverse (meaning the degree of segregation was not total). How did this loose segregation come into existence?

3.2 Land speculation and the retreat of Vietnamese landowners

This section focuses on the plots examined in the 1908 expropriation survey (third stage in Section 2.1) whose origins and transfers for the years 1865 to 1908 can be recovered. It summarizes 62 plots in the expropriation survey of 1908. Of these 62 plots, 29 are in Section A of the Saigon cadastral map, and 33 are in Section H.

3.2.1 Section A

Fig. 8 is a diagram showing the transfers in land ownership from the expropriation survey plots in Section A. Fig. 8 demonstrates that (1) all the plots had initially been public land (local domain, i.e., land belonging to the government of Cochinchina, or state, i.e., land owned by France) and then either maintained that status or were

transferred to individuals or communes, with or without payment; and (2) the transfer of land to the Vietnamese largely took place immediately after colonization.

Fig. 9 shows the ethnic makeup of landowners in 1908. Regarding the expropriation survey plots of Section A, in 1908, the ethnic breakdown of plot ownership was 27.6% European, 24.1% Chinese, 13.8% Indian and 10.3% Vietnamese, while by area it was 27.6% European, 24.1% Chinese, 13.8% Indian and 10.3% Vietnamese.

Fig. 8. Transfers in land ownership in Section A, 1865–1908
(Source: LTQG2. Domaines 10579)

Fig. 9. Ethnic makeup of landowners in Sections A and H

in 1908
(Source: LTQG2. Domaines 10579)

What exactly caused this change in the status quo of the ethnic makeup of landowners? What is noteworthy is the existence of the land speculation boom. For example, lots 66, 67, and 76 in Section A were transferred (in over-the-counter transformation, *vente de gré-à-gré*) from the government of Cochinchina to Delahogue (presumably European) on April 4, 1886 and registered at 116 piasters 78 cents on April 17, 1886. However, after around two months (on June 30), these three lots were sold to Duong Van Tan (presumably Vietnamese) at 800 piasters and were registered on July 1. Ten days later (July 11), these three lots were resold to two (presumably) Chinese brothers, Hui Tang Hung and Hui Tang Chanh, at 1,300 piasters, and registered on July 13 (LTQG2. Domaines. 10579). Altogether, roughly three months after the first transfer, these lots sold twice more between three different races, with the price increasing elevenfold [22]. The striking aspect of the land speculation boom was that the Vietnamese also joined in. In another example, Diệp Văn Cương, a famous “*collaborateur*” and an intellectual bought lots no. 26 from Indian banker (*banquier*) Ka Vena Ajagappachetty at 400 piastres on December 17, 1895, and after one year, on March 31, 1897, Cương resold the lots to the Saigon municipal authority at 800 piastres [23].

The following conclusions can be drawn regarding land ownership in Section A (within the pre-1903 city boundary): (1) Despite having possessed land in the early colonial period, the Vietnamese lost their land in the land speculation boom. (2) Despite not possessing much land in the early colonial period, by purchasing land from other ethnic groups the Chinese and Indians accumulated large tracts of land.

3.2.2 Section H

Does the same pattern hold for Section H (outside the pre-1904 city boundary)? Fig. 10 shows the transfers in land ownership for the expropriation survey plots in Section H. Fig. 10 indicates that some of the plots were sold to people like Trieu Toan, presumed to be Chinese, or Pa Soholingapoullé and Moutariachetty, presumably Indian [24].

Fig. 10. Transfers in land ownership in Section H, 1865–1908

(Source: LTQG2. Domaines. 10579)

It seems that either the Vietnamese did not dispose of their plots, or they tended to sell their land to other Vietnamese. For the expropriation survey plots in Section H, in 1908, the Vietnamese held 72.7% of plots, while the Chinese held 9.1% and the Indians 6.1% (previously listed in Fig. 9, by number of lots). However, it should be noted that Chinese and Indian holdings reveal a clear increase over time, showing that while the number of plots held was small, the scale of plot transfer was large. Comparing land ownership by area, in 1908, the Chinese held 20.9%, while 43.3% was held by the Vietnamese (previously listed in Fig. 9, by area size).

This section has traced the origins of land ownership rights and their transfers for the period 1865 to 1908, incorporating a comparative analysis by cadastral map section. The results indicate that, although land in the center of the city was granted to the Vietnamese upon establishment of the colony, many sold their land during the land speculation boom and the proportion of Vietnamese landholdings declined. By contrast, on the city's outskirts, the proportion of land held by the Vietnamese was steady into the early twentieth century.

4. Conclusion

This study has produced the following conclusions: (1) the legal system (orders and decrees) in the early colonial period had double standards; in the inner parts of the city, the public land disposal system was open to all races, but in the peripheral part of the city the colonial

government designated settlements for the Vietnamese. (2) Despite having possessed land in the central part of the city during the early colonial period, many Vietnamese sold their land because of the land speculation boom of the late nineteenth century. They later sold their land on the peripheries of the city too. These processes led to the lowering of the proportion of land owned by the Vietnamese. (3) Meanwhile, on the peripheries of the city, Vietnamese landholdings continued until the beginning of the twentieth century. This study reveals that the distribution of settlements and the active resale of land by the Vietnamese were the main causes for the uneven distribution of land between races.

The expropriation survey plots under consideration were only a part of the whole of Saigon City, so conclusions of the analysis of the expropriation survey plots were not able to amplify the whole city. Even though it can be pointed out that up to the beginning of the twentieth century, Vietnamese people were generally reluctant to accumulate lands in the inner part of the city, it provides an important point of view to understand the history of southern Vietnam in the colonial period. As is well known, through concession system, indigenous people tended to actively acquire lands in the Mekong Delta from late 19th century to the early twentieth century (Takada 1984: 244-249). Some Vietnamese people at that time thought that the center of their economy was in some cities in Mekong Delta, not Saigon City. For example, when the problem of opening private secondary schools run by the Vietnamese arose, one Vietnamese posted a comment in a Vietnamese newspaper that “Because most part of us (Vietnamese), rich people live in Western provinces (of the Cochinchina), it is too far for student to attend to school, if we open the school in Saigon City.” and “If we open schools at Mỹ Tho or Cần Thơ (Mỹ Tho and Cần Thơ are two of the biggest cities in the Mekong Delta, about 70 and 165 km away from Saigon City) it is convenient for students to go to school because they are near their home.” (*Công Luận* 1920/11/23: 1). Thus, understanding of Vietnamese landholdings in the City during the first half of the twentieth century awaits further investigation.

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Notes

[1] In this article, the term “Vietnamese” people refers to the *Kinh* people, the majority ethnic group of Vietnam, comprising 85.7% of the population at the 2009 census (Ban Chỉ đạo Tổng điều tra dân số và nhà

- ở trung ương 2010: 134). In historical material of the colonial period Vietnamese people were called “*Annamites*” in French. There are two reasons for not using the term *Kinh* people in this article. The first is that the center of the argument of this article is in the relationship between French colonists, Asian immigrants, and *Kinh* people, not in the process of building a nation-state. The second reason is that in Saigon City in the colonial era, the indigenous people were almost synonymous with *Kinh* people, because the number of people belonging to other indigenous minorities was very small. For example, despite the central area of today’s Ho Chi Minh city being originally a town of Khmer people in the colonial era, the number of Khmer people who live in Saigon City is very small.
- [2] One of the factors which induced this difference was that Cochinchina is the only direct colony, while Annam (central Vietnam) and Tonkin (northern Vietnam) were protectorates, and colonization of Cochinchina (1859–1867) progressed about 20 years before the conquest of Annam and Tonkin (1873–1884).
- [3] For a comparison of the municipal organization of Saigon, Hanoi, and Haiphong, see Guillen (1942).
- [4] The Saigon municipal committee (*Commission municipale de Saigon*) was a deliberative body of Saigon City established in 1867. It was transformed to Saigon City council (*Conseil municipal de Saigon*) in 1869 (Ville de Saigon, Secrétaire général de la mairie 1917: 10-11).
- [5] *Công Luận*, or *Công Luận Báo* was a newspaper with a long history. It was first published in autumn 1916, and discontinued in October 1939 (Thạch Phương and Lê Trung Hoa 2001: 828). In 1921, it ran 1,700 copies per issue, making it one of the most popular Quốc Ngữ newspapers (Paycam 2012: 104–106). Compared to other newspapers published by specific political groups or politicians, the tone of the *Công Luận* was less worthy of special mention.
- [6] To be more precise, public lands belonged to the government of Cochinchina, not to communes or municipal offices. Proof of this is that the Quoc Ngu gazette uses “*Nam Kỳ Công Thổ*” as a word meaning public lands (*Gia Định Báo*, 1909/01/04: np.).
- [7] The annual Cambodian population of Saigon indicated on the yearbook was as follows. 13 (1889, *AIF*. 1890 v.1: 64), 58 (1897, *AIF*. 1897 v.1: 564), 46 (1909, *AGI*. v.1: 327), and 75 (1910, *AGI*. Partie administrative: 327). Considering that Saigon was originally “*Pley Nokor*”, a town of Khmer people, these numbers are surprising. The Laotian population was smaller than the Cambodian population. In 1903, only 16 Laotian people lived in Saigon City.
- [8] Thị Nghè canal and Bến Nghé canal are the current names. French sources called these *arroyo de l’Avalanche* and *arroyo Chinois*. Bến Nghé canal were also shown as local names on Hán-Nôm sources in the pre-colonial era (*Gia Định Thành Thông Chí*, v.2, Sơn Xuyên Chí, Trần Phiên An).
- [9] One feature of a Vietnamese traditional city is that cities were political-ritual unions with a center defended by castle walls and a commercial town (Shiraishi 1983: 109–110) (Đàm Trung Phường 2005: 59). In the pre-colonial era, although the Chinese had power in commerce, the Vietnamese were also active in commercial activities (Choi 2004: 73–76).
- [10] After the Lê Văn Khôi revolt (1833–1835), the Gia Định citadel was destroyed by Emperor Minh Mạng and reconstructed on a smaller scale in the northeast corner of the old citadel (Nguyễn Đình Đầu 1998a: 39–41). (Trương Vĩnh Ký 1885: 19).
- [11] For a history of representative architecture built in the colonial era, see Lê Thị Ngọc Ánh (1973).
- [12] In French official gazettes, proper nouns (names of villages, persons) were described only in French and consequently lacked some diacritics of Vietnamese for tones and letters. In this article, proper nouns are described similarly to those historical sources, excluding those cases where the Vietnamese spelling is obvious.
- [13] Tứ Xuân village was the village name as of 1895 (BNF, GE C-2144). Tứ Xuân village was an old village equivalent to the Tứ Xuân hamlet, Bình Trị Thượng canton, Bình Dương district (平陽縣平治上總肆春邑) on the 1836 (17th year of Minh Mạng) land cadastre (Nguyễn Đình Đầu 1994: 208, 260). Over the colonial era, this village was located outside Saigon (or Saigon-Cholon) City boundary.
- [14] Elevations in the article were estimated by map published in 1966 (Nha địa-dư quốc-gia: 1966).
- [15] In the Tân Định-Dakao area, many *Đình*, Vietnamese communal temples, remain today. Some *Đình* were called after the names of villages in those days. (See Hồ Tường and Nguyễn Hữu Thế 2005: 276.)
- [16] Cầu Kho was derived from a warehouse to store the rice tax collected from four provinces – Phan An, Biên Hoà, Vĩnh Thanh, Định Tường – and was established in năm Mậu Thân (1788) (*Gia Định Thành Thông Chí*, v.6, Thành Trì Chí, Thành Gia Định). Chợ Quán was also shown as the local name on Hán-Nôm sources in the precolonial era as the name of the market (*Gia Định Thành Thông Chí*, v.6, Thành Trì Chí, Trần Phiên An) (Trương Vĩnh Ký 1885: 28).
- [17] Because the Cầu Kho-Chợ Quán area was distant from the center of both Saigon City and Cholon City, land readjustment projects were not engaged in very much during the colonial era. Even in the 1930s when Pineau (Georges Pineau) created the project of Saigon City, the Cầu Kho-Chợ Quán area was a sprawling suburban area (075 IFA. Louis-Georges Pineau. PINLO 33/03) (Ota 2005: 289–288).
- [18] After its opening, the avenue was named Galliéni Street (today Lê Lợi Avenue) and Bonnard Avenue (today Trần Hưng Đạo Avenue). These are main roads connecting the centers of Saigon and Cholon.
- [19] Race was determined by identifying full names on historical records in the same period. If full names were not given in other historical records, race was

estimated by the author on the basis of pronunciation and middle names (to distinguish Chinese from Vietnamese) or by initials (to distinguish Indians from other ethnic groups).

- [20] In principal, lands were transferred to individuals by auction (with payment). However, to reward officers who had participated in the construction of the colony or to encourage Europeans to settle there, some lands were transferred without a charge (free concessions). For example, Paulus Huỳnh Tịnh Của, a renowned Vietnamese scholar who converted to Catholicism and worked for the colonial government of Cochinchina, was granted a free plot of land (*Procès-verbaux du Conseil colonial Cochinchine, session ordinaire 1886-1887*: 172). With regard to the transfer of land to communes (villages), it seems that the government of Cochinchina transferred lands without charge. For example, the government transferred plot 46 of section H to the village of Tân Hòa under the title “Public rice field (Công Điền).” Công Điền was a kind of rice field owned by the state, and was delegated to villages and registered as a Công Điền, and was granted to villagers (Nguyễn Đình Đầu 1999: 171). There are no records indicating that the government of Cochinchina imposed a charge for this transfer of land. (LTQG2. Domaines. 10579).
- [21] The details around the creation and amendment of Saigon’s cadaster are unknown. However, according to observations of the land cadastral map of the 1923 edition (075 IFA. Louis-Georges Pineau. PINLO 33/03), it could be said that the entire area of Saigon was divided into seven sections labelled A–G. Each section was then divided into 4–8 streets.
- [22] In the records of plot 85 of Section A, Hui Tang Chanh belonged to “Hui Bon Hoa,” a famously wealthy Chinese landlord from Fujian Province in China who ran a real estate company in Saigon City. Therefore, Hui Tang Hung and Hui Tang Chanh were probably immediate relatives of Hui Bon Hoa (LTQG2. Domaines. 10579).
- [23] “*Collaborateurs*” were Vietnamese who worked with the French in Cochinchina in the nineteenth century (Osborne 1969: xvi).
- [24] Trieu Toan (趙筭) seems to have been a relative of Trieu Cam, who was either a Chinese wholesaler living on Rigault de Genouilly Street in Saigon City, or a rice merchant living on Mytho Street in Cholon City (*ACF*. 1886: 444-453) (LTQG2. Domaines: 10579) (*Gia Định Báo* 1908/08/03: np.). According to their names, Pa Sohlingapoullé and Moutariachetty seem to have been Indian immigrants.

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Application of Remote Sensing and GIS for Monitoring Urbanization and Land Use Land Cover Changes: A Case of Bardhaman Town, Purba Bardhaman, West Bengal

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Abstract: Being a trade-based town and the headquarter of Purba Bardhaman district, Bardhaman reflects a background of unopposed urbanization along with prominent land use land cover (LULC) changes with the passage of time which have been promoted the town to its present situation. This study basically seeks to identify the nature of urbanization and associated changes over land as a result. Geospatial technologies have been employed to detect LULC changes through satellite image classification as well as the growth of built-up areas over time. Statistical software like SPSS is used for the analysis of data. The study reveals shifting of the ancient town from Kanchannagar to Rajbati and the growth of the settlement surrounding Rajbati and both sides of the Banka nala. In 1871 the total population of the town was about 32321 which increased to 334800 in 2011 with an annual and decadal growth rate of 6.02% and 79.40% respectively. There were negative growth rates in the year 1911 and 1921 followed by -7.16% and -3.63% and during 1941 population increased by 60% which was found as highest growth rate.

Keywords: Urbanization, Land Use Land Cover (LULC) change, Geospatial technology.

1. Introduction

Urbanization is a dynamic process of being urban and that is why change over space is inevitable with the passage of time. It basically promotes various changes over an area like changes in population size, socio-economic status, and land use land cover (LULC) especially destruction of vegetation cover, agricultural land, surface water resources along with growth of built-up areas (Grimm et al., 2000). But in this study, urbanization and changes in land use land cover has been taken into consideration. Unopposed urbanization and unplanned growth poses negative effect on environment and its inhabitants over time (Chadchan and Shankar, 2012). Land use land cover changes mainly driven by the natural phenomena and anthropogenic activities, which have an adverse effect on the natural ecosystem (Mukherjee, 1987 and Ruiz-Luna et al., 2003).

To check the environmental consequences of such changes an accurate and up to date monitoring of land use land cover change is necessary (Giri et al., 2005). By the application of geospatial technology like remote sensing such changes over land can be detected through satellite image classification using various GIS software (Roy et al., 2002). Recently, remote sensing has become widely used technique in detecting and monitoring LULC change with useful results (Martha et al., 2008) and it is also very useful for its synoptic view, repetitive coverage and real time data acquisition (Boori and Ferraro, 2015). Satellite imageries are able to enumerate various land use land cover categories accurately and can also help in maintaining spatial data infrastructure for monitoring urban expansion and land use studies (Boori et al., 2014).

The history of urbanization of Bardhaman is very archaic and the seed of urbanization was first implanted by the "Bardhaman Raj Family" (1657-1954). During this time period Bardhaman experienced

noticeable ups and downs in population growth rate and changes over land surface. At present the changes has become more prominent than earlier days.

An attempt towards framing the changes in land use land cover of Bardhaman town have been carried out based on the analysis of remotely sensed data using GIS as a tool for mapping during the time period from 2006 to 2018. The main objective of this present study is monitoring of urbanization especially the growth of built-up areas and detection of other land use land cover changes in a Spatio-temporal context.

2. The Study Area

Bardhaman town has been selected here as the study area for the present study. It is the head quarter of Purba Bardhaman district and located on the Northern bank of Damodar River which covering an area about 26.30 Square Kilometers. At present Bardhaman municipality having 35 wards with a considerable population size around 314265 person and population density about 11949/Km².

Fig. 1. Location map of the study area

3. Material and Methods

3.1 Collection of Data

Landsat-TM (for the year 2006 and 2010) and Sentinel-2 (for the year 2018) satellite images were used for this present study. The character of the images were Multi-resolution, multi-temporal and multi-sensor type (Chander et al., 2009 and Boori et al., 2014). The importance of preprocessing was acknowledged by several studies in performing accurate and reliable change detection analysis (Bastawesy, 2014). The types of data used in this study are given below in table 1.

Table 1. Satellite data type used in this study

Data sets	Date of acquisition	Spatial resolution	Path/Row or Tile No.	Band combination
Landsat-TM	3/12/2006	30 meter	139/44	4,3,2
Landsat-TM	14/12/2010	30 meter	139/44	4,3,2
Sentinel-2	11/11/2018	10 meter	T45QWF	8,4,3

3.2 Image Processing

Several steps were followed towards processing the satellite images like layer stacking to prepare False Colour Composite (FCC) of the images through assigning the correct band combination, creation of Area of Interest (AOI) layer where the entire operations to be performed, subset or clipping of the images based on AOI file to make it ready for the classification of images.

3.3 Classification of Images

After the processing of images, supervised classification method with maximum likelihood

algorithm was performed in ArcGIS 10.4 software. Maximum likelihood algorithm is a popular method used for supervised image classification where a pixel belongs to a particular LULC class. Apart from all there is equal probability for all classes and the input bands have normal distribution. Classified images were corresponded to Google earth for better accuracy of the classification and incorrectly classified pixels were rectified by applying 'recode' method in Erdas Imagine 2014 software. This method is very helpful to check the incorrect classification of any pixel and increases the accuracy level. In this study the LULC classes have been categorized into six groups and the groups are: (1) Built-up Area (2) Water Body (3) Forest and Shrubs (4) Agricultural Land (5) Fallow Land (6) Waste Land. The description of each group that covers different aspect of the land surface is shown below in table 2.

Table 2. Description of LULC classes

LULC classes	Description
Built-up Area	Residential, commercial and services, industrial and transportation
Water Body	River, tanks, ponds
Forest and Shrubs	Big trees and shrubs with small plant
Agricultural Land	cultivable or arable land
Fallow Land	agricultural fallow, residential fallow
Waste Land	marshy or waterlogged areas, industrial wasted areas, barren open patches in the forested area

3.4 LULC Change Detection Analysis

At the post classification stage to detect the changes over LULC classes, a pixel-based comparison was done to get the changing information. The pixels counted for each class were converted into area of the classes to have the outlook of spatial changes with the passage of time. The tabulated form of this change detection analysis is very helpful to get the overview of changes occurring in different land use land cover like growth of built-up areas, decrease in forest cover and water bodies and so on.

Fig. 2. Flow chart of research methodology

4. Results and Discussion

This present study basically shows urbanization and associated changes that have been taken place over the land surface of Bardhaman town during the time period from 2006 to 2018 which not only detect the changes of different LULC classes but also determine the areal extent and spatial pattern of those changes.

There was a considerable rise in urban population of Bardhaman since 1861 which indirectly indicates the growth of built-up area along with other changes. The data provided in the table-3 is showing negative decadal growth rate for the year 1871 (-29.921%), 1911 (-7.1593%), and 1921 (-3.633%). During this period of time several diseases turned into epidemics like malaria, cholera, influenza etc. and the supply of soldier in World War-I took the life of many people and this downfall of population gets back its balance after seven decades. After 1921 there was no downfall in population status. Maximum population growth found in 1941 (58.7915%).

Table 3. Growth of urban population

Year	Urban population	Annual growth (%)	decadal growth (%)
1861	46121		
1871	32321	-3.493	-29.921
1881	32627	0.0943	0.9467
1891	34477	0.553	5.6701
1901	38691	1.1598	12.223
1911	35921	-0.7401	-7.1593
1921	34616	-0.3694	-3.633
1931	39618	1.3588	14.45
1941	62910	4.7328	58.7915
1951	75000	1.7734	19.2179
1961	108000	3.7137	44
1971	143000	2.8469	32.4074
1981	167000	1.5636	16.7832
1991	245000	3.907	45.7066
2001	285871	1.5548	16.682
2011	314265	0.9515	9.9324

Fig. 3. Urban population growth since 1861 to 2011

Fig. 4. Annual and decadal growth rate of urban population since 1861 to 2011

The change detection analysis of LULC reveals noticeable changes over the land surface of Bardhaman town. From given table-4 it is seen that in 2006 built-up area covered 8.8758 Km² which increased to 10.6595 Km² in 2018. The growth was about 7.19%. There was decrease in water bodies from 1.6533 Km² in 2006 to 0.8679 Km² in 2018 and in respect to total area it was about 6.66% to 3.5%. Fall of ground water level and human interference led to dried up of small ponds where maximum of the small water bodies were filled up for construction purpose. Decline in forest cover, agricultural land and waste land are very much prominent. Slight increase in fallow land is found because of conversion of

agricultural land and waste land to fallow land which was carried out by anthropogenic activity.

Table 4. Changes in LULC during the time period of 2006 to 2018

LULC classes	Area in Square Kilometers		
	2006	2010	2018
Built-up Area	8.8758	9.1563	10.6595
Water Body	1.6533	1.1714	0.8679
Forest and Shrubs	4.7695	4.4092	4.0754
Agricultural Land	4.1771	3.3235	2.9548
Fallow Land	1.9492	3.8306	5.3297
Waste Land	3.3803	2.9142	0.9179
Total	24.8052	24.8052	24.8052

Fig. 5. Changes in LULC during the time period of 2006 to 2018

Table 5. Area covered to total area in percentage

LULC classes	Area covered to total area in %		
	2006	2010	2018
Built-up Area	35.78	36.91	42.97
Water Body	6.66	4.72	3.5
Forest and Shrubs	19.23	17.78	16.43
Agricultural Land	16.84	13.4	11.91
Fallow Land	7.86	15.44	21.49
Waste Land	13.63	11.75	3.7
Total	100	100	100

Fig. 6. Percentage of area occupied by LULC classes to total area

A visual outlook of the classified images shows LULC changes in a Spatio-temporal context. Land use land cover map for the years 2006, 2010 and 2018 are provided below to mark the changes (Fig 7-9).

Fig.7. LULC status of Bardhaman town in 2006

Fig.8. LULC status of Bardhaman town in 2010

Fig.9. LULC status of Bardhaman town in 2018

4. Conclusion

This research work examines the urbanization status and land use land cover changes of Bardhaman town, which is known as one of the growing trade-based town of West Bengal. Facilities like working opportunity for day labours, education, medical services and good communication promotes migration and daily haunting of people from the surrounding areas for different purposes which leads to more congestion of town as well as growth of built-up areas and destruction of natural resources like vegetation cover, water bodies and so on. The major problem of the town is unplanned and unopposed growth which may degrade the environmental quality and can promote various health issues. An attempt has been carried out to frame the changes over land surface using geospatial technologies. But further up to date and accurate assessment is required to monitor the changes as well as growth.

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Pattern and Characteristics of Food Insecurity in Rural India

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Abstract: Food insecurity is a global crisis affecting approximately 825 million people worldwide. Sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia shares the largest burden of food insecure population. In this paper, we present the findings of a detailed district level study of eight central states of India. Food insecurity has been analyzed on three dimensions namely availability, accessibility and absorption. With the help of selected indicators for all the three dimensions, indexing and mapping has been done to show the level of food insecurity in rural India. Secondary data sources have been used for the selected indicators. The study concludes that food insecurity in rural India is not randomly distributed, rather there is a contagious zone. Among key factors, geography is a major determinant for food insecurity in rural India. To overcome the problem, a series of measures has also been suggested which require working on all the three dimensions.

Keywords: Food Insecurity, Sub-Saharan Africa, South Asia, India.

1. Introduction

Food is the first basic need of the human being. However, globally there are 825 million hungry people who are not able to satisfy their hunger. Sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia shares the largest burden of this hungry people. India, even after more than six decades of planned development and recent record of high growth and agricultural production, is struggling hard to provide the security of this basic need to its populace. With more than 237 million food-insecure people, India is home to the largest number of undernourished people in the world (FAO, 2010). India ranks 65th among the 79 developing countries and countries in transition on Global Hunger Index (GHI) 2012. Another recent report HUNGaMA by Naandi Foundation reported 42% of under five children as underweight and 59% as stunted in the country which compelled the then Prime Minister to call it a national shame. The food insecurity and hunger thus raise serious questions of human rights.

Though the need for the food and its insecurity has been experienced right since the existence of the humankind, the development of definition, conceptual framework and analysis of food security is very recent. Nearly four decades before, food security was conceived as merely its availability in sufficient quantity. However, later on it was agreed that food security is not just the matter of the availability of food, but even more of the access of households and individuals to sufficient nutritious food. The absorption of food as nutrition in the body is further mediated by access to safe drinking water, and hygienic sanitation facilities. Consequently, food security is analyzed along the axes of availability, access and absorption. The importance of entitlements in food security is further underlined by the Supreme Court's judgments validating the Right to Food. As a signatory to the UN's Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), the Government of India and all state governments have an obligation to reduce by half the proportion of people suffering from hunger by 2015.

2. Objectives, Indicators and Methods

The objective of the study was three-fold. Firstly, it was to identify the regions and social groups most affected by food insecurity. Secondly, suggest policy interventions appropriate to improving food security for those regions and social groups and finally selection of indicators and methodology to measure food insecurity at the district level. The identification of suitable indicators attracted lots of debates and discussions. The availability of data at district level on these indicators was also a crucial factor in identifying indicators of measuring food security at sub-state level. Finally, a set of twelve indicators were identified. There were four availability-related indicators. These were agricultural production in per capita value terms, proportion of forest area, extent of irrigation and rural connectivity in terms of villages with access to paved roads. The six variables considered for the access-to-food dimension include proportion of agricultural labourers, proportion of Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes, ratio of working age population, monthly per capita consumption expenditure, casual wage rate of rural persons and female literacy rate. Access to safe drinking water and primary health services are the two variables considered for the absorption index.

All indicators included along three dimensions of the food security have been scaled and normalized (to make them unidirectional) to take a value on a scale ranging from 0 to 1. The scaled least achievement corresponds to zero, whereas the best achievement corresponds to 1. For three selected variables, viz., percentage of agricultural labourers to all labour and proportion of ST and SC population and percentage of forest area to total geographical area, the reverse figure (per cent of non-agricultural labour to total workers; per cent of non-ST & SC to total population; and per cent of non-forest area to total area) have been used. Likewise, the variable dependency ratio has also been reversed.

After calculating the index of each variable, averaging of the indicators resulted to give each of the three dimensions of food security. The composite Food

Security Index is again derived by averaging all the selected indicators. The values of 281 districts across all the eight states were combined to develop a food security index. Subsequently, districts were ranked on the basis of their composite score. These scores were then categorised into five equal groups namely – Secure, Moderately Secure, Moderately Insecure, Severely Insecure and Extremely Insecure. The choropleth techniques were used to portray the pattern of food insecurity in India.

3. Rationale and Limitations

The study attempted to fill a vacuum of analysis of the food security at the sub-state level on the three axes of availability, access and absorption. Prior to this, most of the attempts have been made at macro level. However, some of the critiques of the study points out that the indicators used are very dynamic and changes rapidly over the period of time. So, the district level analysis requires continuous updation with the onset of new datasets. Secondly, the study has also used many proxy indicators in the analysis in the unavailability of data on direct indicators.

4. Pattern of Food Insecurity

The pattern of food availability is presented in Figure 1. As can be seen, the plateau, forested, desert and tribal-dominated area of the eight states are extremely insecure. The northeastern part of Madhya Pradesh, northern Chhattisgarh, Bundelkhand region of Uttar Pradesh, Jharkhand and northwestern part of Odisha which share these characteristics form a contiguous region of the extremely insecure in terms of food availability. The Gangetic river valley of Uttar Pradesh and Bihar and Narmada valley regions of Madhya Pradesh are relatively secure in terms of food availability.

Fig. 1. Food Availability Map of Rural Central India

Similarly, one can observe geographical distribution of the food access index which emerged from the six different indicators. Even from this perspective, the extremely insecure regions are the forested and tribal regions of Chhattisgarh, Odisha, and some parts of Madhya Pradesh and Maharashtra. Some regions of Maharashtra, Rajasthan and a district of Raigarh in

Chhattisgarh have been found to be secure. One can also observe a contiguous belt of severely insecure districts spread across Madhya Pradesh, Chhattisgarh, Jharkhand, Odisha and Bihar (Figure 2).

Fig. 2. Food Access Map of Rural Central India

The geographical distribution of the food absorption index can also be seen in specific groups (regions). Here, the area of Bundelkhand, the plateau region of Jharkhand and Chhattisgarh and desert region of Rajasthan are extremely insecure in terms of food absorption or utilization. Severely insecure districts are in most of the cases adjacent to the extremely insecure districts. At the other extreme, Bihar, western Uttar Pradesh and parts of Maharashtra are relatively secure in terms of the food absorption index (Figure 3).

Fig. 3. Food Absorption Map of Rural Central India

The combination of the three dimensions provides us a food security index which has been presented in Figure 4. One can widely discern the pattern of food secure and food insecure regions in the map. Three extremely food insecure regions can easily be identified. The first region, which is a relatively largest contiguous region, extends from the eastern part of Madhya Pradesh to Chhattisgarh, Odisha and Jharkhand. While a substantial share of these states are food insecure – with the entire Jharkhand (all 18 districts), 13 districts of Chhattisgarh, 29 districts of Madhya Pradesh, 19 districts of Odisha and 11 districts of Bihar. The second extremely insecure region is in the southern part of Chhattisgarh and southwestern part of Odisha largely consisting of Bastar,

Dantewada and the Kalahandi-Balangir-Koraput (KBK) regions of Odisha. The third region of extremely food insecurity, a relatively smaller one, is in the southwestern part of Madhya Pradesh particularly constituted by the Jhabua and Barwani districts. Nearly all these regions are dominated by the tribal population. At the other extreme, southern Maharashtra, northwestern Uttar Pradesh and northeastern Rajasthan are found to be food secure regions.

Fig. 3. Food Security Map of Rural Central India

Since district is the unit of programme implementation at the sub-state level, the study had set out to identify districts that are food insecure and that need priority intervention. But, the results show that food insecure districts are not randomly distributed in districts rather it forms a distinct contiguous region largely determined by the geography. For instance, the people dwelling in the hill-forest and plateaus were found to be the most food insecure. This is so for all the states covered. Both the desert and the semi-arid Deccan Plateau are regions of generally depressed agrarian conditions.

5. Characteristics of Food Security

Some of the common characteristics which is shared by the food insecure regions in comparison to the better-off regions are extent of low irrigation, poor connectivity in terms of paved roads, the hill-forest and plateaus having high proportion of ST population, areas with high proportions of SCs and agricultural labourers and low agricultural wages, and overall lower levels of female literacy. So, in a way the study not only identified districts with food insecurity but also it also tries to point out factors which lead to food insecurity. It can at least help us identify actions that need to be taken to bring the food insecure regions at par with the food secure regions.

The study argue that the point of identifying the geography of hunger is not to suggest that 'geography is destiny' but to draw attention to the constraints that have to be overcome in order to eliminate or even reduce hunger. A low productivity of rain-fed foodgrain production, which is the source of own entitlements for small and marginal farmers, can make the people even

more vulnerable when there is a high variability of rainfall and consequently of production too in rain-fed agriculture. In general, however, the rural areas of districts of these eight states fare poorly on nutritional outcomes. It is only the more urbanized and industrialized districts and the irrigated districts that do better. Thus, ensuring food security and improving the nutritional status is a challenge for the rest of these states as a whole. The study emphasize the fact that the identification of certain districts for priority action does not mean that either resources or efforts to bring up all districts can slacken, but only draws attention to the need for more inclusive growth efforts and the special efforts needed to bridge the divides between different regions and districts of the state.

6. Food Security Interventions

The study not only identify priority districts for food security interventions in selected eight states of India but also suggest some policy interventions. In India, the right to food is realized through two sets of measures: employment schemes to increase incomes and thus access to food, complemented by National Food Security Act, 2013 (NFSA) which includes subsidised food grain distribution, Mid-Day Meal Scheme (MDM) and the supplementary feeding in the ICDS centres. While working for the improvement in the functioning of these government schemes, it is important to link these schemes, and other interventions, with the development process in the country.

Access to roads and irrigation are two areas in which the hill-forest districts fall considerably behind the country. Rural connectivity and small-scale irrigation in a manner appropriate to hill regions, along with improvement in female literacy, should form the core of efforts to reduce extreme poverty, and thus hunger, in the hill-forest districts of the country.

Along with this, special efforts are needed for development of livelihoods of forest-based populations. This itself comprises a number of measures, including implementation of the Forest Rights Protection Act so as to provide security of tenure, investment to enable a shift to production of high value crops, shortening the chain of intermediaries and promoting value-added processing in non-timber forest products (NTFP) etc. The changes in production that would reduce food insecurity require not just improved access, but also enhanced capabilities, through extension and technological development, building on local capacities and knowledge. Complementary steps need to be taken to enhance women's agency in the household and community, through literacy and education and women's land rights. Enhancing women's capabilities could, among other benefits, also lead to the adoption of improved nutritional practices, such as exclusive breast-feeding of infants till six months of age.

Micro-finance, through self-help groups (SHGs) supported by NGOs, could help reduce the incidence of inter-linked transactions. This will improve the food security situation by enabling borrowing for critical needs, and also increase the share of household income under the control of women. Overall, there are three issues of land reform that need to be tackled in order to improve food security. First is to restore illegally-acquired tribal lands, secondly distributing the land to landless, largely Scheduled Castes (SCs), and finally provision of security of tenure of Scheduled Tribes (STs) in forest areas.

Some of the plain regions of the states have a large proportion of agricultural labourers in the rural workforce. Schemes of distribution of agricultural land to the landless, including women, would help in improving access of the rural poor to food and thus reduce food insecurity. Increasing productivity in common lands, often unmanaged pastoral or otherwise degraded lands, would also increase food security.

In the large semi-arid belt, e.g. in the Marathwada and Vidarbha regions of Maharashtra and the central plains of Madhya Pradesh, the agricultural production is largely rainfed. It is also the area which has seen large numbers of farmers' suicides. Revitalizing this agriculture is a necessary step to reduce food insecurity, as that would increase both employment of labour and wage rates. Employment programmes (e.g. NREGA schemes) can themselves be planned to improve infrastructure to provide needed public goods (roads), or quasi-public goods (irrigation) for the area.

It is finally argued that improvement in the implementation of these government schemes depends, at one level, on improvement in administration and governance systems. But more important is the role of the people who are to benefit from the schemes, whether organized through CBOs, NGOs or traditional tribal bodies – in both demanding and monitoring implementation of the numerous schemes. The innovative *mitanin* system of Chhattisgarh and similar such schemes in other states, can be extended to support better implementation of all government schemes. Enhancing capabilities, through rights, access to resources and training, will clear the road for building the capacity to aspire – the aspirations for a better life exist, but the means or capacity to realize those aspirations are lacking.

7. Conclusions

The study helped to understand that it is the geography which still determines the level of food security in rural India. The Government of India has taken number of programmes to overcome geography and ensure food security. The recently launched NFSA, 2013 has ensured the subsidized food distribution to more than 800 million people in India. This Act is transformative for the fact that for the first time in the history of India, the food has become a right for its people. If the Act gets

implemented properly, it is hopeful of reducing the burden of hunger and food insecurity to the large extent. Besides, there are also employment generation, poverty alleviation related initiatives which is trying to lessen the impact of poverty and hunger among Indian people. The need is to implement these programmes in its true spirit.

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Demography in the Cotton-Producing Area of Kazakhstan Amid the Great Famine

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Abstract: The Great Famine of the 1930s is one of the most significant and tragic events in the history of Kazakhstan. Previous studies have mainly argued about the political decisions and causes of the tragedy, although no major spatial approach has been conducted to date. Pianciola importantly argued that the division of economic regions established by Gosplan separated the conditions between the Kazakh economic region and the Central Asian economic region (Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, and Kyrgyzstan). He constructed this hypothesis by comparing semi-nomadic groups in Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan. This paper attempts to inspect Pianciola's hypothesis by comparing cotton-producing areas in Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan. The results generally confirm Pianciola's hypothesis: The cotton-producing area of Kazakhstan was more seriously damaged than that of Uzbekistan. This paper, based on GIS (Geographic Information System) demographic reconstruction and archival document analysis, concludes that economic differences between Kazakhstan and other Central Asian republics, including food supply, caused mass population outflow from the cotton producing area of Kazakhstan.

Keywords: Kazakhstan, Famine, Cotton, Population, Soviet History.

1. Introduction

The Great Famine of the early 1930s is one of the most significant and tragic events in the modern history of Kazakhstan. Although this event is now well known, the importance of the Great Famine was not openly discussed until the end of the 1980s when Glasn osti began. Abylkhozhin, Kozybaev, and Tatimov's famous article, "Kazakhstanskaya Tragediya" (1989), contributed to the rediscovery of the famine and the calculation of the related depopulation. They estimated that about 1,750,000 Kazakh people died in the famine. Although this number is often quoted in following papers, the number is not based on regional data but the authors estimated death toll with some demographic assumptions. For example, they assumed that mortality in the Great Famine was ten times larger than usual. The lack of quantitative data in 1930s make demographic survey difficult as described below ⁽¹⁾.

This work was followed by a series of historical studies by other researchers and publications on historical documents in Kazakhstan, Russia, Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan, and so on (ex. Abdiraimov et al. 1991; Kozybaev et al. 1998; Danilov et al. 2000, 2001; Alimova 2006). One of the most important descriptions of the famine comes from the secret report submitted from Ryskulov to Stalin in March of 1933. Ryskulov's report quoted various documents, including internal papers from within the Soviet bureaucracy, described tragic situations in detail (Ryskulov 1984: 320-348). Other secret reports were found in national and regional archives and published mainly in post-Soviet countries.

As described below, the Soviet demographic data from 1930 is quite confusing and incomplete, but even one volume summary of the 1937 census indicates the severe damage of the Kazakh population between 1926 and 1937 (Table 1). Table 1 shows that the population decreases between the two sets of census data for each republic are largest in Kazakhstan followed by Ukraine. Among the 11 Soviet republics at that time, only Kazakhstan and Ukraine experienced republic-level depopulation between those two census reports. The census of 1937 shows that Kazakhstan lost about 16% of its total population and Ukraine lost about 2%. Though the Ukraine famine, known as *Holodomor*, is more well-known than the Kazakh famine because of a series of related books and films, this table suggests that the Kazakh situation might have been more severe than *Holodomor* ⁽²⁾.

2. The Kazakh Great Famine and Spatial Questions

As to the Great Famine, many researchers have discussed the policy making of the time. In other words, who was responsible for the famine, and did that person or group intend for it to happen? Most likely, the leader of Kazakhstan at that time, Goloshchekin, or perhaps Stalin himself was responsible for the tragedy, but recent research has shown that the decision-making process was more complex (Cameron 2018: 5-6).

Concerning the famine in the early Soviet period, another question has been emphasized as well. If any person or group was responsible for the famine, did they intend to commit "genocide" against the Kazakh nation? Needless to say, this question is intertwined

with the political situation of each of the post-Soviet states.

Researchers have published various papers and monographs about this problem. For example, Pianciola published a series of articles about decision-making and the chain of commands (Pianciola 2004, 2017, 2018). He argued that “the logic of the situation naturally led in the direction of plundering the Kazakhs, beyond racism and ethnic tensions” within a system of administration (Pianciola 2004: 187). In 2018, Cameron published a monograph titled “The Hungry Steppe,” arguing that the Soviet regime’s role in the Great Famine was crucial and that the enormous and irreversible damage to the Kazakh society and Kazakh nomadism in the early Soviet era was an outcome of continuous social and environmental changes in the Kazakh society under Russian imperial rule. Russian settlers who entered the steppe gradually changed the nomadism of the Kazakh people, and these changes made the Kazakh economy more vulnerable to social and natural disasters (Cameron 2018).

Although decision-making and various causes of the Great Famine have been focused on by most researchers concerning this event, other important issues have been relatively less emphasized. In 2016, Cameron surveyed research trends and pointed out that spatial analysis is one new direction in this field. Wheatcroft, a historical demographer who researched *Holodomor* and the Kazakh Great Famine, started GIS-based demographic research on the Kazakh Great Famine, but the status of the project remains uncertain (Cameron 2016: 126–127) ⁽³⁾. Cameron also confirmed that spatial analysis is necessary to clarify the characteristics of the Kazakh famine in her monograph. She argued that the lands of central Kazakhstan which was the major place for Kazakh cattle breeding were hit particularly by the famine (Cameron 2018: 171, 175).

Concerning the spatial question of the Great Famine, Pianciola importantly argued that the division of economic regions established by Gosplan differentiated the conditions between Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan ⁽⁴⁾. Although semi-nomadic lifestyles were common to the Kazakhs and the Kyrgyz, the famine had a greater impact on the Kazakhs in the Kazakh economic region (defined as the grain-producing and livestock-breeding region) than on the Kyrgyz in the Central Asian economic region (defined as the cotton-producing region and comprising Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, and Kyrgyzstan) (Pianciola 2017: 82-85, 89).

This paper examines Pianciola’s hypothesis by comparing cotton-producing areas located in the Kazakh economic region and the Central Asian economic region. Former studies argued that the ill-prepared collectivization of the nomads and the requisition of grain and livestock were the main reasons for the famine (Pianciola 2004: 154-156, 161-165). The first research question of this paper is thus, “Was depopulation concentrated in the grain-producing and livestock-breeding region?” In other words, “Did the

cotton-producing area within the Kazakh economic region escape depopulation?”

Table 1. Population change from the 1926 census to the 1937 census (%)

Source: *Vsesoyuznaya perepis' naseleniya 1937 g. kratkie itogi*, Moskva, 1991, pp. 54–61.

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3. Cotton-Producing Areas in Kazakhstan in 1930s

Figure 1, based on the document of the Kazakh Gosplan, shows that the economic regions of Kazakhstan in early 1930s were clearly divided into three regions. The northern region was characterized by the production of field crops, with the main crop being grain. The central region was characterized by livestock breeding. The southern region was characterized by industrial crops including the cultivation of cotton, fruits, and vegetables.

Figure 2, based on another Kazakh Gosplan document, shows cotton-producing areas in Kazakhstan

in 1932, which were very concentrated in part of the southern region. If grain and livestock requisition were the main reasons for the famine, that begs another research question: “Did the cotton-producing area escape the famine or, at least, were cotton farmers in Kazakhstan less damaged by it?”

It has been confirmed that the cotton-producing area was more favorable to the Soviet regime than other village areas. In 1927, the Soviet regime thought that cotton production in Kazakhstan must be expanded in future (Cameron 2018: 64). Ryskulov, mentioned above, wrote that the cotton-producing area of Kazakhstan received more intensive investment than did other areas (Danilov et al. 2001: 506). In 1932, Isaev, prime minister of the Kazakh ASSR, mentioned cotton production as one of the most important tasks (Abdiraimov et al. 1991: 149).

Fig. 1. Economic regions of Kazakhstan by district (raion) in 1931

Source: TsGA KR, F. R-962: Gosplan KASSR, op. 1, d. 1243, l. 6–8.

Fig. 2. Cotton-producing areas in Kazakhstan in 1932

Source: TsGA KR, F. R-962, op. 1, d. 742, l. 76.

It is noteworthy that the Soviet regime gave special priority for the food supply to the cotton-producing areas in Kazakhstan before the Great Famine. For example, the regime planned to supply 67,000 tons of grain to about 70,000 families of cotton farmers in 1930 (TsGA KR, F. R-962, op. 1, d. 742, l. 6). On the other hand, the Soviet regime planned to requisition 1,000,000 tons of grain from Kazakhstan in the same year (Danilov et al. 2000: 666). Operators of the grain requisition often stole necessary food and seed (Danilov et al. 2001: 258–260).

The cotton-producing area in the Central Asian economic region also had special priority concerning the food supply. Before the Russian revolution, the cotton production in Russian Central Asia, mainly in the Ferghana valley, flourished, but after the Revolution (the long civil war between the Red Army and the Basmachi movement) the cotton production was almost annihilated by 1922.

The Soviet regime was successful in the recovery of cotton production in Central Asia by the end of 1920s. Although the regime used police power to force farmers to produce cotton, the special priority for the food supply was one of the causes of the recovery of cotton production. In the 1920s, food shortages often occurred in the village areas in Central Asia. Due to the frequent food shortages, the food supply for cotton farmers had great importance⁽⁵⁾.

Demography in this period also shows the specificity of the cotton-producing area of the Central Asia economic region. In Uzbekistan, the population increased from 1926 to 1939 in the Fergana valley, where cotton production was concentrated; this was higher (38%) than the average of Uzbekistan (28%) (Perepis' 1926 XV 1928: 3; Perepis' 1939 1992: 26).

4. Demography Amid The Great Famine

Spatial demographic analysis on the Great Famine is difficult because of the lack of historical sources. In 1926, the first census of the USSR was conducted, and its result was systematically published. The 1926 census includes district- (raion-) level demographic data, but we cannot get comparable census data from the 1930s. The 1937 census shows depopulation in some republics (Table 1). The Soviet regime did not allow for the publication of the results of the 1937 census because the mass depopulation clearly shows the failure of the Soviet economic policy. Two years later, the 1939 census was conducted, but an analysis of these data is even more difficult because the census was designed to conceal the depopulation, throwing the results into doubt.

Although the summary of the 1937 census in one volume was published in 1991, the comparison with other census data at the level of minor districts has not yet been possible. Frequent border changes in all district levels in the early Soviet period have also made comparison difficult.

When the Second World War occurred, mass immigration and economic replacement happened throughout the territory of the USSR. Central Asia and Kazakhstan were two of the main regions where factory equipment and labor were evacuated from the European part of the USSR. During the war, Germans, Chechens, and Crimean Tatars lived in various part of USSR were forced to immigrate to Kazakhstan (Cameron 2018: 172). Because of WWII, the postwar census is not useful for the reconstruction of the demography in the 1930s. In short, we cannot utilize demographic data at the district level in the 1930s from official census

publications. This means that we must find other historical sources to analyze the spatial demography amid the Great Famine.

This paper uses the documents of Gosplan of the Kazakh Autonomous Soviet Socialist Republic, which are kept in the Central State Archive of the Republic of Kazakhstan. The population data recorded in the Gosplan document are more sporadic and less systematic than census information and the methods for gathering information and their reliability are doubtful. Nevertheless, these data are important for historical research simply because other quantitative data are unavailable. This document records the estimated population on 1st January 1932 and 1st January 1933. The method of data collection and the process of statistical estimation remains unknown (TsGA KR, F. R-962, op. 1, d. 874, l. 7-9).

Figure 3 shows population changes in rural regions in Kazakhstan from 1932 to 1933. Blue circles and their sizes represent population decreases and their scales. The few red circles represent population increases. Figure 3, based on one archival document of the Kazakh Gosplan, shows population changes in 117 districts of Kazakhstan. This suggests that depopulation was recorded in almost all districts throughout all three agricultural areas shown in Figure 1. The cotton-producing area in Figure 2 also experienced depopulation during this period.

Fig. 3. Population changes in rural regions in Kazakhstan from 1/1/1932 to 1/1/1933

Source: TsGA KR, F. R-962, op. 1, d. 874, l. 7-9.

Fig. 4. The result of hot spot and cold spot analysis on the result of Fig. 3.

Source: TsGA KR, F. R-962, op. 1, d. 874, l. 7-9.

Note: Red color suggests high values cluster that means population increase and blue suggests low values cluster. Dark red and blue mean higher confidence level of spatial cluster.

Hot Spot Analysis by ESRI ArcGIS⁽⁶⁾, shown in Figure 4, does not suggest demographic differences between the northern and southern regions. The Hot Spot Analysis tool calculates the Getis-Ord G_i^* statistic for each feature. The resultant z-scores and p-values suggest where features with either high or low values cluster spatially. This type of analysis points out that a hot spot of population change did exist in the eastern end of Kazakhstan; in some districts in the eastern area, about 50% population increases were recorded within a year. These unusual increases can be explained by mass migration of refugees amid the Great Famine toward the Chinese Xinjiang (Ryskulov 1984: 320). One document estimates 200,000 fled to China from Kazakhstan in the end of the 1920s and the early 1930s (Pianciola 2004: 170-171).

As mentioned above, we do not have sufficient census information from the 1930s that can be compared to the 1926 census. This paper thus compares the 1932–1933 population list to the 1926 census, although a direct comparison between the Gosplan document and the 1926 census is impossible because the former consists of 117 spatial units and the latter, 450. Furthermore, the Gosplan document lacked information about the precise territory of each district but did record the names of the administrative centers, while the 1926 census includes both the territory map of the local administration and a map of its center. This paper uses GIS to connect these data by comparing the population of the 450 points of the 1926 census in each of the 117 areas based on a Voronoi diagram (Figure 5). Needless to say, this comparison is not perfect because the borders of the local territories of the two sets of data are not equal, but a difference of population in any unit must be compensated for by differences in neighboring units. For that reason, we can suppose that the result of this calculation (Figure 6) suggests the general tendencies of the population change from 1926 to 1933.

Fig. 5. Local centers in the 1926 census and the Voronoi map based on the place name list of the Gosplan document

Source: *Vsesoyuznaya perepis' naseleniya 1926 goda*, Tom VIII; TsGA KR, F. R-962, op. 1, d. 874, l. 7–9.

Fig. 6. Population changes in rural regions in Kazakhstan from 1926 to 1933

Source: *Vsesoyuznaya perepis' naseleniya 1926 goda*, Tom VIII; TsGA KR, F. R-962, op. 1, d. 874, l. 7–9.

Figure 6 shows population changes in rural regions in Kazakhstan from 1926 to 1933. The sizes of the blue circles represent the scale of population decreases, and the red circles represent population increases. The Hot Spot Analysis prepared in ESRI ArcGIS could not find any hot spots from population changes, nor from related ratios, as shown in Figure 6. In other words, all rural subregions of Kazakhstan were ravaged by severe depopulation. The change of total population in each district suggests that the southern cotton-producing districts were not exempt from the countrywide depopulation.

Figure 6 includes only rural population data; urban population in this period might have increased because of mass migration of refugees. The document that Figure 6 is based on did not record any data about urban populations, but other reports recorded a mass influx of refugees into capitals and major cities. For example, in March of 1933, Mirzoyan, secretary of the Communist Party of Kazakhstan, reported that thousands of refugees had flowed into the cities of Aulie-Ata, Turkestan, Kзыr-Orda, Alma-Ata, Petropavlovsk, Gur'ev, Akmolinsk, Karaganda, and so on (Abdiraimov et al. 1991: 197–198).

In general, the mass depopulation shown in Figure 6 is the result of deaths and refugee outflows. Ryskulov recorded the approximate number of transborder refugees from Kazakhstan in March 1933; 40,000 in the Volga Region, 50,000 in West Siberia, 20,000 in Karakalpakstan, 100,000 refugees in Kyrgyzstan, and 30,000 in “Central Asia” (meaning Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, and Tajikistan). He stressed that there were many refugees in other regions including Chinese Xinjiang, as well (Ryskulov 1984: 320).

The results found from the total population are ambiguous and can be interpreted in a variety of ways. The lack of ethnic population data is critical. It is well known that the victims of the Great Famine of Kazakhstan were ethnic Kazakhs, especially Kazakh nomads and semi-nomads (Cameron 2018: 178). On the other hand, a large number of Russian and other ethnic

peasants were forced to immigrate to Kazakhstan from the European part of the Soviet Union. Pianciola estimated that between 200,000 and 250,000 people were deported to Kazakhstan in the two-year period 1930 to 1931 (Pianciola 2004: 157-159). These ethnic compositions are invisible in the total population data, and further survey on archival documents is necessary in the future in order to obtain demographic data that includes ethnic composition.

5. Why Were The Cotton-Producing Areas in Kazakhstan Hit By Depopulation?

Figures 4 and 6 suggest that, concerning population changes, it is difficult to find any difference among the three economic regions shown in Figure 1 or the special status of the cotton-producing regions in Figure 2. Unlike Cameron's exceptions (Cameron 2018: 171), the total population analysis did not show the hardest condition of the central part of Kazakhstan⁽⁷⁾. Although the Soviet economic system accorded special priority to cotton farmers by supplying grain, the GIS maps show that cotton-producing regions also suffered from severe depopulation. Why was the special priority of the food supply unable to save cotton farmers in Kazakhstan from severe depopulation in the early 1930s?

Some cotton-producing districts of Kazakhstan, such as the Suzak district, experienced fierce anti-collectivization movements from 1929 to 1931 (Abdiraimov et al. 1991: 143; Pianciola 2004: 160). Such political disorder could have affected the demography of the region but severe depopulation continued from 1932 to 1933 too (Figure 4). The anti-collectivization movement from 1929 to 1931 could not explain this continuous population decrease by 1933.

Some archival documents suggest that there was an important difference between Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan, which was a part of the Central Asian economic region. An archival document shows that the grain supply per family of cotton farmers in Kazakhstan was less than half of that given to families in Central Asia in 1928–1929 (TsGA KR, F. R-962, op. 1, d. 742, l. 10). In Uzbekistan, one family of cotton farmers actually received 600–700 kg of grain a year. In Kazakhstan, the Soviet authorities planned to supply each family with 540 kg, but in actuality, they could only supply 140 kg in 1928 and 300 kg in 1929. In the same period, various commodities were circulated only in markets in Uzbekistan. The Kazakh authorities and population had to cross the Kazakh–Uzbek border to get necessities.

Another document shows that the authorities requisitioned the grain supplied to cotton farmers through a coercive campaign (TsGA KR, F. R-30: Sovnarkom KASSR, op. 1, d. 908, l. 19). In 1933, Ryskulov and other reporters from the northern part of Kazakhstan wrote that this type of fierce grain

requisition occurred not only in cotton-producing regions but also in all of Kazakhstan (Ryskulov 1984: 325, 333; Abdiraimov et al. 1991: 121) ⁽⁸⁾. These documents confirm that the economic situation in the cotton-producing area of Kazakhstan was worse than that in similar areas in Uzbekistan ⁽⁹⁾.

Other documents indicate that depopulation occurred in some cotton-producing areas in Kazakhstan. A short document reported that about 500 families migrated from the cotton-producing regions of Kazakhstan to the cotton fields of Central Asia in April 1931 (TsGA KR, F. R-962, op. 1, d. 1243, l. 41). Ryskulov also wrote that 250 houses in one of the cotton-producing areas of Kazakhstan (Pakhta-Aral) were uninhabited because of food shortages (Ryskulov 1984: 338).

6. Concluding Remarks

This study attempted to reconstruct demographic changes before and amid the Great Famine and found ubiquitous characteristics of population decrease throughout the territory of Kazakhstan. The cotton-producing region in Kazakhstan was not excluded from this depopulation. Though clear differences were not found between northern and southern regions, GIS hot spot analysis suggests that there were demographic movements to the eastern end of Kazakhstan that can be explained by the large flow of refugees toward Chinese Xinjiang. Because of its limited sources, this study could reconstruct only the total population numbers and could not analyze ethnic factors.

This study argues that economic differences between Kazakhstan and four Central Asian republics resulted in mass migration. The special priority of the food supply in the cotton-producing districts of Kazakhstan was not enough to stop the depopulation. Even though the conditions of cotton-producing areas may not have been as poor as or even marginally better than other regions in Kazakhstan, the cotton fields in Central Asia were much better in comparison.

This study does not deny that the failure of Soviet economic-agrarian policy in Kazakhstan that especially hit the Kazakh nomads was the main reason of the Great Famine but emphasizes that direct effects of the Soviet policy could not fully explain the local economic conditions. The argument of Pianciola is one of the possible explanations that can fill the gap between the Soviet policy and the local condition. While Pianciola (2017) argued that economic regionalization by Gosplan led to differences in the conditions of seminomads in Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan, this study suggests that it also led to differences in the lives of cotton farmers in Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan.

Acknowledgment

This work was supported by JSPS KAKENHI Grant Number 19K23125.

Notes

- [1] Researchers continued estimating the death toll of the Kazakh Great Famine but the results varied from 1.3 to 2.5 million (Cameron 2018: 201, Pianciola 2004: 137; Davies and Wheatcroft 2004: 412, Kozybaev 1998: 15).
- [2] For example, see Conquest (1986) and the film Mr. Jones (2019). Cameron (2018: 4-5) summarized several reasons for the emphasis on Ukrainian case.
- [3] Davies and Wheatcroft (2004). Wheatcroft gave a presentation about his GIS project in Japan in 2013.
- [4] Gosplan was the organization in the Soviet government that gathered economic information and developed economic plans based on it.
- [5] These two paragraphs are based on Ueda (2014: 26-28) and Ueda (2016).
- [6] <https://pro.arcgis.com/en/pro-app/latest/tool-reference/spatial-statistics/h-how-hot-spot-analysis-getis-ord-gi-spatial-stati.htm>
- [7] Though Cameron's argument includes the resettlement of refugees in the southern part of Kazakhstan after 1933 (Cameron 2018: 171-172, 245), this paper analyzed the data by 1933.
- [8] The Soviet organization forcibly requisitioned grain not only from Kazakh farmers and semi nomads but also pure nomads who did not plant any grain. Nomads were forced to sell their livestock to prepare grain for requisition. The catastrophe of nomadism caused by this condition was one of the direct causes of the Great Famine (Ryskulov 1984: 333; Pianciola 2004: 159-161).
- [9] The cotton-producing region of Uzbekistan also had severe economic problems and social unrest in this period. There were over 70 anti-collectivization demonstrations in the Ferghana valley from February to March of 1930 (Alimova 2006:87-96, 195-198).

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Editorial Note

JANGIS is the peer reviewed annual journal of the *Asian Network for GIS-based Historical Studies, Japan*. The Journal is exploring new research fields with the applications of Geographical Information System (GIS) in Historical as well as other social sciences. We welcome ambitious contributors interested in interdisciplinary studies for publication in JANGIS using GIS.

[BIPLAB BISWAS]

ANGIS 2018 - International Conference, INDIA
Department of Geography
The University of Burdwan, Burdwan, INDIA

Date: 29th November 2018	
Venue: Bardhaman Science Centre Auditorium	
Time	Programme
9:00 AM-10:00 AM	Registration
10:00 AM-11:15 AM	Inaugural Session
11:15 AM-11:30 AM	<i>Coffee/Tea Break</i>
11:30 AM-12:30 PM	Special Lecture 1: Chairperson: Prof. Amaresh Dubey, JNU, New Delhi Speaker: Prof. Mamta Sanghamita, Hon'ble MP, Lok Sabha Topic: Evolution of Indian Administrative Structure with Special Reference to <i>Panchayati Raj</i>
12:30 PM-1:30 PM	Special Lecture 2: Chairperson: Prof. Bupinder Zutshi, JNU, New Delhi Speaker: Prof. Tsukasa Mizushima, Tokyo University, Japan Topic: Population and Colonial Development in India
1:30 PM-2:30 PM	<i>Lunch Break</i>
2:30 PM-3:30 PM	Special Lecture 3: Chairperson: Prof. Tsukasa Mizushima, Tokyo University, Japan Speaker: Dr. Tapati Banerjee, Director, NATMO, India Topic: Historical Archaeology in India - A Geospatial Connectivity to review the temporal dimension
3:30 PM-5:00 PM	Panel Discussion 1: Theme: GIS-Connecting Geography, History & Economics.....Looking Beyond Where - I Chairperson: Prof. Amaresh Dubey, JNU, New Delhi Panellists: Prof. Mondira Dutta, JNU, New Delhi Prof. Sayako Kanda (Keio University, Japan) Dr. Soumya Bandyopadhyay (RRSSC, Kolkata) Prof. Bupinder Zutshi, JNU, New Delhi
5:00 PM-5:30 PM	<i>Coffee/Tea Break</i>
5:30 PM-7:30 PM	Cultural Programme
7:30 PM-8:30 PM	<i>Dinner</i>

Date: 30th November 2018	
Venue: Geography Department, The University of Burdwan	
Time	Programme
9:00 AM-11:30 AM	Technical Sessions: 1,2,3
11:30 AM-1:30 PM	Panel Discussion 2: Topic: GIS-Connecting Geography, History & Economics.....Looking Beyond Where - II Chairperson: Prof. Amaresh Dubey, JNU, New Delhi Panellists: Prof. Tran Thanh HA, Vietnam National University, Hanoi Dr. Abhay Kumar, Lokashraya Foundation, New Delhi Dr. Anil Kumar Roy, Associate Professor, CEPT, Ahmedabad
1:30 PM-2:30 PM	<i>Lunch Break</i>
2:30 PM-4:30 PM	Technical Sessions: 4,5,6
4:30 PM-5:00 PM	<i>Coffee/Tea Break</i>
6:00 PM-7:00 PM	Executive Committee Meeting, ANGIS
Date: 1st December 2018	
Venue: Geography Department, The University of Burdwan	
Time	Programme
9:00 AM-11:30 AM	Technical Sessions: 7,8,9,10,11
11:30 AM-12:30 PM	Special Lecture 4: Chairperson: Prof. Amaresh Dubey, CSRD, JNU, New Delhi Speaker: Prof. Kuntala Lahiri-Dutt, ANU, Australia Topic: Geography, Interdisciplinarity, and the Social: Thoughts about a New GIS
12:30 PM-1:30 PM	Valedictory Ceremony Chairperson: Prof. Kuntala Lahiri-Dutt
1:30 to 2:30 PM	<i>Lunch</i>

Technical sessions programme schedule
30th November 2018

Time: 9:00 AM-11:30 AM

Technical Session: 1

Sub-Theme: Landscape Dynamics

Venue: Hall-2

Chairperson: Dr. Anil Kumar Roy, CEPT, Ahmedabad

Rapporteur: Ms. Nabanita Mukherjee

Sl. No.	Title of the Paper	Presenter	Co-Presenters
LDY 1	Reassessment of Ancient Tieu Tuong River (Bac Ninh province) on Historical Data and Geography Information System (GIS)	Nguyen Thi Hue	Nguyen Quang Anh
LDY 2	Land Suitability Analysis (LSA) for Rice crop in West Bengal	Chiranjit Singha	Kishore Chandra Swain and Sayan Choudhury
LDY 3	Population Pressure on Landuse/Landcover Dynamics of Chilika Catchment, Odisha – A Geospatial Approach	Adikanda Ojha	Jajnaseni Rout
LDY 4	Predicting the Land use and Land cover change using Markov model: A catchment level analysis of the Bhagirathi- Hugli River	Sanat Das	Rajib Sarkar
LDY 5	Evaluating Past and Present Scenario of forested landscape in Bengal Duars, India	Koyel Sam	Namita Chakma
LDY 6	Land use/land cover Modeling and urban growth dynamics in Kanksa C.D. Block, Paschim Bardhaman District, West Bengal	Shyamal Dutta	Sanat Kumar Guchhait
LDY 7	Controls of anthropogenic activities on the stream power distribution: An analysis of River Damodar, India	Sumantra Sarathi Biswas	Padmini Pani
LDY 8	Application of Remote Sensing and GIS for Monitoring Urbanization and Land Use Land Cover Changes: A Case of Bardhaman Town, Purba Bardhaman, WB	Ashis Dhara	Biplab Biswas

30th November 2018

Time: 9:00 AM-11:30 AM

Technical Session: 2

Sub-Theme: Historical Studies & Societal Behaviour

Venue: Hall-3

Chairperson: Prof. Kalyan Das, OKDISCD, Guwahati

Rapporteur: Ms. Bhaswati Mondal

Sl. No.	Title of the Paper	Presenter	Co-Presenters
HES 1	Changing Rural Landscapes and Dependency on Agricultural Land: A Study of West Bengal	Padmaja Mondal	
HES 2	Technology Trap and Sustainability in Agriculture	Barun Kumar Paul	Gopa Samanta
HES 3	Guilty until Proven Innocent: Relocating the Fourth World in the Indian Caste Strata	Vishwajit Giri	
HES 4	Changing Nature of Spatial-Structure of Rural Settlement in Salanpur, Paschim Bardhaman, West Bengal	Sumana Nandi	Tapas Mistri
HES 5	Historical legacy of Insitu Diaspora and Cultural transition of Bengali Community in the frontier zone of Jharkhand	Rahul Patra	Sanat Kumar Guchhait
HES 6	Disparities of Household Condition and Status of South 24 Parganas, West Bengal, India	Ujjwal Dutta	
HES 7	Dynamics of Education: An Inter Generational Study of Change and Trend in Dhekia Gram Panchayat, Saltora C.D. Block, Bankura District	Ayanika Sarkar	Biswaranjan Mistri

30th November 2018

Time: 9:00 AM-11:30 AM

Technical Session: 3

Sub-Theme: Geo-heritage, Geoarchaeology and Tourism

Venue: Hall-1

Chairperson: Dr. Premangshu Chakraborty, Department of Geography, Visva Bharati

Rapporteur: Ms. Alokanda Ghosh

Sl. No.	Title of the Paper	Presenter	Co-Presenters
GGT 1	Ruins and Spatiality in Kinnaur, Western Himalaya	Uttam Lal	
GGT 2	A Geo-Historical Journey of Delhi from Painted Grey Ware Pottery Culture to Mughal Period	Sonali Ghosh	Anjana Bandyopadhyay & Tapati Banerjee
GGT 3	Can culture be mapped? A quest to discover the blurred boundaries between the cultural zones of Kolkata	Debika Banerjee	
GGT 4	An Enquiry into the Causes of Loss of Historically Important Towns of India	Rajnish Kumar	
GGT 5	The present status of tourism in Sundarban, India using Spatial Technology	Panchanan Das	Jatisankar Bandyopadhyay
GGT 6	Historical Places of Chilka Lake	Krupasindhu Bhatta	Jajnaseni Rout & R. N. Samal
GGT 7	One step to conserve History Application of GIS in unwrapping the potentialities of the Historical Assets in Deganga Block, North 24 Parganas, India	Sanjali Das	Anu Rai
GGT 8	Application of GIS in Tourism Circuit Planning of Geoarchaeological Sites	Rahul Mandal	Premangshu Chakraborty
GGT 9	Modernisation strategies of a Decayed Historic Town by Rejuvenating its Cultural Heritage	Chandrima Bandyopadhyay	Gopinath Bhandari
GGT 10	Knowledge based Information Retrieval of Geolocation for Emergency Response Services	Akansha Saklani	Harish Karnatak

30th November 2018

Time: 2:30 PM-4:30 PM

Technical Session: 4

Sub-Theme: Landscape Dynamics

Venue: Hall-1

Chairperson: Prof. Giasuddin Siddique, BU

Rapporteur: Ms. Akansha Saklin

Sl. No.	Title of the Paper	Presenter	Co-Presenters
LDY 9	Study of Direction and Magnitude of Exponents of Internal Drivers in Channel sensitivity of Fluvial Dynamics: A Case Study of Darjeeling Himalayan Foothill Streams, Darjeeling, West Bengal	Subhadip Gupta	
LDY 10	Mapping Gains and Losses in Vegetation using Landsat TM Imagery along the State Highway of Purbasthali I CD Block, WB: A Temporal Analysis	Prasenjit Pal	Biswaranjan Mistri
LDY 11	The Vedic Saraswati River: Tracing the Paleo-course and Desiccation through Maps and Satellite Imageries	Prakash Mistri	Shrabani Das & Somasis Sengupta
LDY 12	Study of Palaeochannels of Damodar River in West Bengal, India: Application of Historical Evidences and Remote Sensing	Prasanta Kumar Ghosh	N C Jana, Sujoy Bandyopadhyay & Ritendu Mukhopadhyay
LDY 13	Pattern of Sediment sorting for Transfer Mechanism of Sand-sized Bed Load: A Reach Scale Analysis	Priyabrata Das	Varsha Degharia & Subhadip Gupta
LDY 14	Estimation of Spatial Pattern of Vegetation Cover and its Relationship with Surface Temperature in Burdwan Town and Surroundings-A Geospatial Analysis	Sanu Dolui	Sumana Sarkar
LDY 15	Changing Pattern of Drainage System with Special Reference to Human Interferences in Gosaba C.D. Block, South 24 Parganas, West Bengal	Soumen Ghosh	Biswaranjan Mistri
LDY 16	Remote Sensing and GIS in Landscape Characterization of Rajaji National Park, Uttarakhand	Biswarupa Ghosh	

30th November 2018

Time: 2:30 PM-4:30 PM

Technical Session: 5

Sub-Theme: Historical Studies & Societal Behaviour

Venue: Hall-2

Chairperson: Prof. Sayako Kanda, Keio University, Japan

Rapporteur: Dr. Rajesh Raushan

Sl. No.	Title of the Paper	Presenter	Co-Presenters
HES 8	Demographic Changes in Kazakhstan during the Great Famine	Akira UEDA	
HES 9	Study on the formation and development of human settlement patterns in the lower of the Red River Delta, Vietnam: An application of GIS and Remote Sensing	Tran Thanh Ha	Vu Hong Le
HES 10	The History of Indo-Fijian Diaspora: Reflections on the Literary Writings	Arnab Kumar Sinha	
HES 11	Temporal Analysis of Changes in Socio-economic Status in Goalpara Village	Mahuya Sen	
HES 12	Hand Hygiene and Health Awareness in Bikrampur Gram Panchayat of Simlapal CD Block, Bankura, West Bengal	Somenath Kar	Biswaranjan Mistri
HES 13	Crime Hotspot Mapping and Predictive Analysis: A Case Study of Shimla City	Ritvik Chauhan	Vijay Kumar Baraik

30th November 2018

Time: 2:30 PM-4:30 PM

Technical Session: 6

Sub-Theme: Climate Change

Venue: Hall-1

Chairperson: Prof. Bupinder Zutshi, JNU

Rapporteur: Mr. Aman Arora

Sl. No.	Title of the Paper	Presenter	Co-Presenters
CCI 1	Trends in Temperature and Precipitation in the 20th Century of Malda, India	Mousumi Naskar	
CCI 2	Risk Assessment of Climatic Variability Applying Livelihood Vulnerability Indices: Realities from Sagar Island	Nabanita Mukherjee	Aritra Basak, Arindam Roy, Mehedi Hasan Mandal & G. Siddiqui
CCI 3	Climatic Variability in Formation and Spatial Changes of Purbasthali Lake	Mehedi Hasan Mandal	Arindam Roy, Subhendu Ghosh, Sumanta Bid & G. Siddique
CCI 4	Impact of Climate Change in the Livelihood of Indigenous and Marginalised Communities of Nepal	Madhab Giri	

1st December 2018

Time: 9:00 AM-10:00 AM

Technical Session: 7

Sub-Theme: Landscape Dynamics

Venue: Hall-1

Chairperson: Dr. Biswarupa Ghosh, BKC College, Kolkata

Rapporteur: Mr. Subhadip Gupta

Sl. No.	Title of the Paper	Presenter	Co-Presenters
LDY 17	Past is the key to the future: Landslide Inventory	Harjeet Kaur	Srimanta Gupta, Surya Parkash and Raju Thapa
LDY 18	Determining flood inducing capacity of tributary basins of Mayurakshi River based on morphometric properties using GIS	Aznarul Islam	Suman Deb Barman
LDY 19	Temporal monitoring of land cover change and its impact on water resources in south part of Iran	Maryam Naghdzadegan Jahromi	Mojtaba Naghdzadegan Jahromi, Sajad Jamshidi
LDY 20	Impact of sand mining on habitat destruction and transformation: A case specific study on Kangsabati River, West Bengal, India	Raj Kumar Bhattacharya	Nilanjana Das Chatterjee
LDY 21	Systematic assessment of 2014 flood hazard in Rapti River Basin, Middle Ganga Plain, Uttar Pradesh, India using Geospatial Technology	Aman Arora	Manish Pandey, Masood Ahsan Siddiqui
LDY 22	An Assessment of Geomorphological Diversity of Island Landforms in South Andaman District with Special Reference to Havelock & Neil Island, India using Geospatial Techniques	Anurupa Paul	JatiSankar Bandyopadhyay & Ashis Kumar Paul

1st December 2018

Time: 10:00 AM-11:00 AM

Technical Session: 8

Sub-Theme: Trade Relations and Trade Routes

Venue: Hall-1

Chairperson: Dr. Biswarupa Ghosh, BKC College, Kolkata

Rapporteur: Mr. Suvadip Gupta

Sl. No.	Title of the Paper	Presenter	Co-Presenters
TRT 1	Visualizing the Salt Market and Trade Routes in Early 19th Century Bengal and Bihar	Sayako Kanda	
TRT 2	Corporate Green Marketing- Tokenism of Brand Promotion or Helping the Environmental Awareness?	Rajesh Das	
TRT 3	Linking Space over Time: A Historical Overview of Mass Transport Network Development in Kolkata City	Teesta Dey	
TRT 4	Metropolitan Shadow on Suburban Train Commuting: A Study from Howrah-Bardhaman Main Railway Line	Bhaswati Mondal	Gopa Samanta
TRT 5	Dividing Ocean: An Attempt of Making Maritime Security and Its Failure among the Mughals and Europeans	Shinsaku Kato	
TRT 6	Dynamic Simulation of Urban Expansion based on Cellular Automata and Markov Chain Model: A Case Study of Siliguri Metropolitan Area, West Bengal	Apurba Sarkar	Pradip Chouhan

1st December 2018

Time: 9:00 AM-10:00 AM

Technical Session: 9

Sub-Theme: Historical Studies & Societal Behaviour

Venue: Hall-2

Chairperson: Dr. Anil Kumar Roy, CEPT, Ahmedabad

Rapporteur: Mr. Prakash Mistri

Sl. No.	Title of the Paper	Presenter	Co-Presenters
HES 14	Outbreak of Malaria in Atiabari Tea Garden: A Geographical Examination of Probable factors	Rajesh Kerketta	Biplab Biswas
HES 15	Incidence of Child Marriage in Md Bazar CD Block, Birbhum District, West Bengal: A Study on the Light of Sustainable Development Goals 2030	Rabiul Hoque Molla	Biswaranjan Mistri
HES 16	Empowerment of Namasudra Women Through Education And Employment: A Study With Spatial Reference To Banshihari CD Block, Dakshin Dinajpur, West Bengal, India	Arabinda Roy	
HES 17	Spatial and Gender Variation in Population Growth in India: Emerging Trend and Future Direction	Rajesh Raushan	

1st December 2018

Time: 10:00 AM-11:30 AM

Technical Session: 10

Sub-Theme: Resources & Economy

Venue: Hall-2

Chairperson: Dr. Anil Kumar Roy, CEPT, Ahmedabad

Rapporteur: Mr. Prakash Mistri

Sl. No	Title of the Paper	Presenter	Co-Presenters
REN 1	Colonial Intervention and Deterioration of Agriculture and Agrarian Relation in Bengal: A Critical Evaluation	Anjan Chakraborti	
REN 2	Evaluation of Dynamics of Ground Water Table Using GIS: A Case Study	Sribash Tikader	
REN 3	Microwatershed Management of Ansupa Catchment: A Geospatial Approach	Jajnaseni Rout	Adikanda Ojha
REN 4	Identification of suitable sites for growth of Green Spaces in a part of Varanasi District using High Resolution Remote Sensing Data	Jitendra Kumar Jaiswal	
REN 5	Quantification of Groundwater Recharge and Potential Zone identification in a selected part of Hugli District using Remote Sensing and GIS	Biswajit Das	S. Malik, R. Chakraborty, S C Pal
REN 6	Soil Organic Carbon Mapping using Regression Analysis and Remote Sensing Data	Gouri Sankar Bhunia	Pravat Kumar Shit, Hamid Reza Pourghasemi & Mohsen Edalat

1st December 2018

Time: 9:00 AM-11:30 AM

Technical Session: 11

Sub-Theme: Resources & Economy

Venue: Hall-3

Chairperson: Dr. Abhay Kumar

Rapporteur: Koyel Sam

Sl. No.	Title of the Paper	Presenter	Co-Presenters
REN 7	Identifying the Potential Areas for Establishing New Health Care Facility Centres in Murarai-I CD Block, Birbhum District, West Bengal	Alokananda Ghosh	Biswaranjan Mistri
REN 8	India's Employment Garentee Scheme and Women Participation	Kriti Arora	
REN 9	Micro scale Entrepreneurs into the Vicious Circle of Mahajani System: A Study on Bell Metal Industries of Bankura District, West Bengal	Papiya Manna	Tapas Mistri
REN 10	Agricultural Land Conversion, Out-Migration and Growth of Census Towns: A Study of Murshidabad District, West Bengal	Kiran Kumar Roy	Gopa Samanta
REN 11	Internal Migration in India: Data and Trends	Manasi Bera	
REN 12	GIS and the new media: The emerging trend	Mugdha Sengupta	
REN 13	Present Scenario Of Human-Elephant Conflict: A Case Study Of Bankura North Forest Division, West Bengal	Jhantu Mondal	Deb Prakash Pahari
REN 14	The Housing Options of the Migrant Informal Labours of Kolkata City	Sumita Roy	
REN 15	Application of GIS in Rural Developing Planning in Bihar with Special Reference of Kishanganj District in Bihar	Anup Kumar Sharma	

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4. The length of an article should be around 10,000 words including footnotes and references. Abstract around 200 words should be submitted along with the full paper.
5. The text should be typed single-spaced in 9 point type in Times New Roman.
6. Tables should be digital in EXCEL file and inserted within the main text. Figures (maps, photos, etc.) should be submitted in EMF or JPEG file and be inserted within the main text. Tables and Figures should be numbered consecutively in the following way.
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7. The title of the Table should be above the Table. The title of the Figure should be below the Figure. Notes and Sources should be written below Table or Figure.
8. Sources of references or quotations should be indicated in the text as follows: (Stein 1984: 185).
9. Footnotes, if any, should be numbered consecutively.
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 - Mizushima, Tsukasa. 2008. "Ecology and Society", *International Journal of Economic History*, 14(5), pp. 34-56.
 - Utsunomiya, F. 2012. "Chinese Migrants in Kobe", in Mayama, S. (ed.), *Migration in Asia*, Tokyo: Tokyo University Press, pp. 78-101.
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Presidential Remarks.....i

A Note from General Secretary - ANGISii

The Asian Network for GIS-based Historical Studies, Asia or ANGIS (Asia).....iii

Economic Geography of Joint Stock Companies in British India, 1907-1938..... 1

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